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**A Study Examining the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety and
Enjoyment in Relation to Speaking Skills of Thai Postgraduates
Studying in the TESOL Program in the United Kingdom**

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Dissertation as Part of the MA

in Applied Linguistics and TESOL In Service

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List of Abbreviations

ASR: Automatic Speech Recognition

EI: Emotional Intelligence

EFL: English as a Foreign Language

ERT: Emergency Remote Teaching

FLCAS: Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale

FLCA: Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety

FLE: Foreign Language Enjoyment

FLES: Foreign Language Enjoyment Scale

FLA: Foreign Language Anxiety

FLB: Foreign Language Boredom

IELTS: International English Language Testing System

LOTE: English and Languages Other Than English

SLA: Second Language Acquisition

TESOL: Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages

WTC: Willingness to Communicate

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Abstract

The emotional experiences of Thai TESOL postgraduate students in the UK are investigated in this study, with particular attention paid to the effects of Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety (FLCA) and Foreign Language Enjoyment (FLE) on English speaking abilities. With a foundation in the ground-breaking ideas of Horwitz et al. (1986) regarding FLCA and Dewaele et al. (2014, 2022, 2023) regarding FLE, this study evaluates the impact of these emotional dimensions on language acquisition in a sample of fourteen Thai TESOL students. The Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), the Foreign Language Enjoyment Scale (FLES), and semi-structured interviews were used in this mixed-methods study to collect data. Seven of the fourteen participants took part in in-depth interviews, offering qualitative insights into how their experiences learning a language interacted with feelings of anxiety and enjoyment. With the goal of providing a thorough understanding of the difficulties and inspirations that students encounter while studying overseas, the research looks at several psychological, educational, and social elements that may have an impact on these emotional experiences. The results imply that FLCA has a major impact on students' speaking abilities, frequently impeding their ability to participate fully and perform well in speaking assignments. On the other hand, FLE seems to improve their motivation and involvement, which is good for their language skills. These findings highlight the need of instructional techniques that ease students' anxiety and increase enjoyment in the classroom, and they imply that teachers working in multicultural and multilingual environments might gain from incorporating these ideas into their methods. The research recommends changes in teaching strategies to provide a more supportive and engaging learning environment, therefore enhancing educational outcomes for foreign language learners. It does this by recognising emotional triggers and useful coping mechanisms.

1. Introduction

1.1 Aims of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to explore the emotional experiences of Thai TESOL postgraduate students in the UK, focusing specifically on Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety (FLCA) and Foreign Language Enjoyment (FLE). This research seeks to identify how these affective factors influence students' acquisition and use of English as a foreign language, particularly their speaking skills. Through understanding the specific challenges and joys these students encounter, the study aims to provide insights that can help in designing more effective language learning environments that are sensitive to the emotional needs of learners.

1.2 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study draws on the seminal works of Horwitz et al. (1986) who introduced the concept of FLCA, and Dewaele et al. (2014, 2022, 2023) who extensively researched FLE. This research framework combines these foundational theories with current educational practices to examine the interplay between anxiety and enjoyment in learning English as a foreign language. It considers various psychological, pedagogical, and sociocultural variables that may impact the emotional experiences of Thai TESOL students in the UK.

1.3 Structure of the Dissertation

The dissertation is organized into five main chapters to provide a comprehensive exploration of the emotional experiences of Thai TESOL postgraduate students in the UK. The Introduction sets the stage by outlining the study's aims, conceptual framework, research questions, and overall structure. Following this, the Literature Review delves into existing studies and theories on FLCA and FLE, with a particular focus on how these affect speaking skills in a foreign language. The Methodology chapter details the research design, participant selection, data

collection methods, and analytical procedures employed. The Results chapter presents the findings from the data analysis, highlighting the levels and impacts of FLCA and FLE among the students. Finally, the Discussion and Conclusion chapter discusses the implications of these findings for teaching practices and future research, summarizing the study's contributions to language education.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

In the field of language education, the need to understand the emotional experiences of learners has gained paramount significance for fostering effective learning environments. Leading researchers in this area have been Elaine Horwitz (Horwitz et al., 1986, 1988, 2001) and Jean-Marc Dewaele (Dewaele et al., 2014, 2022, 2023), among others. Horwitz's seminal study in 1986 positioned Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety as a unique anxiety state that had such powerful impacts on students' functioning and engagement. That is why research conducted by Dewaele has demonstrated how Foreign Language Enjoyment boosts motivation and success in language learning through the induction of positive emotions (Dewaele et al., 2022, 2023).

Despite such valuable contributions, it remains inconclusive and calls for additional investigation in the literature concerning the emotional experiences of Thai university students in foreign language classroom. These students typically face challenges that come with cultural adaptation, language barrier, and pressure from postgraduate studies, which can make the anxiety much more intense and, in some cases, result in a negative impact on the learning experience. Yet research specifically focusing on this demographic is limited. However, it was only studied by Chinpakdee (2015) and Bhattarachaiyakorn and Phettakua (2023).

Drawing upon the fundamental theories of Horwitz and Dewaele, my research is aimed to investigate the levels of FLCA and FLE among Thai TESOL postgraduate students in the UK.

This study aims to understand a more nuanced perspective of the emotional experiences among this student population to help educators design and develop more supportive teaching strategies. The understanding of ways in which these students navigate their emotional landscape may foster better educational outcomes and a positive learning environment.

Besides contributions from Horwitz and Dewaele in this field, other researchers have also played critical roles in highlighting the emotional dimension related to language learning. For example, MacIntyre & Gardner (1994) have shown that anxiety interferes with cognitive operations, such as memory and information processing, which come into play especially during vocabulary acquisition. Al-Khotaba et al. (2019) and Gregersen & Horwitz (2002) further researched the relationship between speaking anxiety, fear of making mistakes, and performance in speaking tasks, thus showing how pervasive anxiety is among language learners.

On the contrary, research by Dewaele et al. (2022) and Botes et al. (2023) finds out that FLE lowers anxiety, increases willingness to communicate, and academic performance (Dewaele et al., 2022). Favourable teacher behaviors boost FLE and improve learner attitudes (Botes et al., 2023). Secondly, FLE enhances classroom creativity and engagement (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2014)

This research aims to investigate the concerns relating to the emotional experiences of Thai TESOL postgraduate students in the UK. Through a review of the most recent empirical studies, by which to critically synthesize and identify the research unexplored areas, the study will result in the formulation of the research questions that work to understand such emotional challenges and joys these students could have.

2.2 Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Definitions

Elaine Horwitz, Michael Horwitz, and Joann Cope define in their seminal work of 1986 Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety (FLCA) as anxiety precipitated by the foreign language learning situation. There are three elements making this kind of anxiety different from general anxiety: communication apprehension, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation. Such elements are crucially related to cognitive and emotional learning. Furthermore, Horwitz et al. (1986) developed the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) as a significant tool for measuring the intensity of anxiety felt by language learners and to understand how it affects their performance and, more generally, their learning process.

Afterward, FLCA has been described as “the feeling of tension and apprehension specifically associated with second language contexts, including speaking, listening, and learning” (MacIntyre & Gardner, 1994, p. 284). Such an anxiety ordinarily affects language performance and can partially influence cognitive processing in language learning settings. Studies have shown that FLCA can disrupt students' ability to process and produce language efficiently, and therefore it undermines language development and the performance of learners in academic tasks.

FLCA is defined by Horwitz (2017) as “a distinct complex of self-perceptions, beliefs, feelings, and behaviors related to classroom language learning arising from the uniqueness of the language learning process” (p. 27). Botes et al. (2023) define it as an anxiety situation that has specific characteristics to the situation occurring in learning a foreign language. The FLCA was characterized by trait-like consistency and long-term stability; individuals experiencing this type of anxiety are likely to feel it persistently across various language learning situations. Tsui & Cheng (2022) mention that FLCA operates within the context of situation-specific anxiety—meaning the nature of classroom language learning causes the complex construct.

They argued that specific situational variables in the language class, such as peer dynamics, teacher behavior, and task demands, are instrumental in creating the experienced anxiety.

Moreover, Horwitz (2017) notes that FLCA is driven by the threatening nature of using a foreign language to the ego, and it causes learners to feel discomfort since they are not able to represent themselves authentically. It is especially strong in speaking activities and is said to be the most anxiety-provoking part of any foreign language class compared to reading, writing, or listening by students. The inability to bring out one's real personality and intentions in a foreign language can result in heightened self-consciousness and fear of judgment, driving anxiety.

FLCA has been seen to interfere with language processing during both the input (listening and reading) and output (speaking and writing) phases. As an example, Dewaele (2017) found that anxiety could be responsible for harming learners' comprehension and production capacities, resulting in significant reductions in language acquisition. This kind of anxiety impacts on the cognitive load of processing language and on the emotional resilience of learners, who may be more acutely stressed by the real-time communication challenges of speaking than by the longer-term demands of writing. Two main manifestations of FLCA in classroom experiences can be distinguished: one that affects writing and leads to long-term setbacks and another that affects speaking and causes immediate communication difficulties because of the real-time nature of the challenge.

The classroom environment and the behavior of the instructor play a crucial role in influencing FLCA. It plays a very important role in creating positive or negative classroom climates and instructor behaviors that can really impact students' anxiety levels and, therefore, their learning experiences. An inclusive, supportive, and engaging teaching approach can reduce anxiety to a significant level, while, inversely, a focus on rigorous error correction and performance

evaluation increases anxiety. Dewaele, Saito, and Halimi (2022) argued that the behavior of the instructor and classroom climate are important in modulating the levels of anxiety and so the learning experience of students; this would call for lower stress and higher engagement in pedagogical strategies.

In the broader setting of language learning, then, the development of FLCA would be crucial. FLCA can be much higher due to an interpersonal element related to learning in a face-to-face classroom. Conversely, emergency remote teaching (ERT) introduces additional stressors such as technological issues and isolation, profoundly impacting anxiety levels. The research study by Dewaele et al. (2024) proceeds to determine how different contexts may in fact be responsible for the determination of impact on FLCA, with the relation between triggers for and presentations of FLCA being very contextual.

Pedagogical interventions that are directed and personalized can thus alleviate such circumstances. Horwitz et al. (1986) recommended community language learning and suggestopedia for creating less stressful learning environments. These approaches minimise the reliance on performance so that the learner can gain from the language and discover it in a more relaxed and less anxious manner. Furthermore, Cheng (2008) underscores the importance of positive feedback and structured guidelines to help learners maintain confidence in their language abilities, crucial for mitigating FLCA.

Understanding the psychological aspect of FLCA is fundamental when forming interventions that could potentially be used to improve language learning and educational attainment. The relationship between FLCA and other emotional factors, such as motivation and self-esteem, is high. Dewaele & Saito (2019) conducted a research study where it was discovered that participants reporting higher levels of self-perceived language proficiency were showing lower

levels of anxiety and greater enjoyment in the learning process. It gives a hint that FLCA could be prevented by increasing learners' confidence in their linguistic competence.

In fact, educators can be effective at controlling FLCA by teaching in a manner that creates a friendly and supportive climate in the classroom, where constructive feedback and building a community mitigate anxiety and encourage learner participation. Cultural and contextual factors are also central; Dewaele's (2019) cross-cultural study showed that different educational and social contexts may impact the seriousness and ways in which FLCA is manifested, thereby indicating cultural sensitivity in pedagogical approaches is needed.

Indeed, more ultimately, FLCA needs to be solved in ways broader than just to alleviate the anxiety in the classroom. This will involve making language learning better for students in ensuring overall well-being and successful learning. These would need a comprehensive approach that appreciates the multifaceted nature of FLCA, teaching strategies personalized to each one, and an educational policy that considers mental health and the well-being of learners.

2.3 Foreign Language Enjoyment Definitions

Foreign Language Enjoyment (FLE) has emerged as one of the cardinal concepts in Second Language Acquisition (SLA) that focuses on the positive emotion's learners have in engaging a new language Zeng (2021). Unlike Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety (FLCA), which emphasizes the stress and anxiety associated with language learning, FLE highlights the joy and satisfaction learners derive from the process. FLE is defined as a multifaceted phenomenon encompassing cognitive, emotional, and social components that collectively foster a more engaging and effective learning experience (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2014).

The nature of FLE is involved in the pleasure derived from the sounds, rhythms, and accents in the mastery of a new language, from communicating with people of other cultures, and in overcoming challenges in language that come along. For example, Dewaele & MacIntyre (2014) highlight that FLE is not just the absence of negative emotions but a discrete positive affective state that enhances creativity and engagement in the classroom.

Several causes of variation affect the amount of FLE felt by students, one being individual difference in personality. Another cause includes pedagogical strategies employed in class and classroom climate and interaction between the teacher and students. For example, extroversion-related traits were highly correlated with FLE, and the outgoing are likely to feel more at ease when the learning environment is more interactive. Pedagogical practices using humour, praise, and communicative exercises are employed in enhancing more FLE in terms of creating a supportive and involving environment for learning (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2019).

The influence of FLE goes beyond mere individual enjoyment to wider educational outcomes. For example, if students enjoy the class, they are more likely to remain interested in the classroom, engage in risks when using the language, and be more motivated and persistent in their work. Such attitudes foster increased academic performance and better connectedness in the language community, which helps to fulfil language programs' educational goals overall (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2014).

For example, research on FLE and affect longitudinally by Chengchen Li & Li Wei (2021) with junior secondary learners in rural China, indicate that FLE is a significant predictor of language achievement over time, and this effect is stronger than for anxiety or boredom. They had found evidence of FLE through positive impacts on learner motivation and engagement is associated with better language learning outcomes. They found that although anxiety had a

short-term negative impact, FLE provided a longer-lasting positive effect in language classrooms. Thus, this shows how important it is to cultivate enjoyment in language classrooms.

FLE can be enhanced by using teaching strategies that will strive to deliver the best environment for students. Such strategies involve the use of pedagogical skills that will stimulate challenges in students, but which simultaneously offer the necessary support and feedback for success. Educators are recommended to design activities that are fun and relevant to learners' interests, promoting an environment that enhances FLE (Dewaele & Dewaele, 2020).

In summary, FLE significantly enriches the language learning experience by integrating joy and satisfaction into the educational process. Understanding and harnessing the drivers of FLE allows educators to enhance their teaching methods and curricula, fostering not only linguistic competence but also emotional well-being and a positive attitude towards learning a new language. Ongoing research into FLE is expected to continue revealing insights into how to facilitate enjoyable and effective language learning experiences (Dewaele et al., 2024).

By examining the multifaceted nature of FLE and its drivers, educators can design more engaging and effective curricular experiences. For example, praising students' achievements and promoting a positive classroom atmosphere can significantly enhance FLE. Research also indicates that addressing both positive and negative affective aspects in language learning can boost educational attainment by offsetting anxiety and boredom. During the COVID-19 pandemic, studies have shown that physical classroom presence improves FLE and reduces FLCA, highlighting the importance of learning context (Dewaele et al., 2024).

Ultimately, FLE fosters a more engaging and effective learning environment, drawing from Dewaele's studies (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2014, 2019). Accordingly, promoting FLE should be a central focus for educators aiming to enhance the language learning outcomes of Thai TESOL postgraduate students. Other researchers, such as Chengchen Li & Li Wei (2021), have investigated learning environments that boost FLE in classroom settings in China, which can be related to the Asian cultural context of Thai participants in this research. Furthermore, a recent study by Dewaele et al. (2024) agreed that teaching methods and classroom atmosphere can noticeably improve FLE.

2.4 Empirical Studies

2.4.1 Studies FLCA

Since the definitions of FLCA and FLE have been set in the previous section, this chapter further explores related empirical studies to yield an insightful and nuanced understanding in this area of study. This discussion is of particular importance to Thai TESOL postgraduate students as it investigates the interplay between anxiety and enjoyment in the experiences of learning a language.

Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986) laid the groundwork for understanding FLCA by identifying it as distinct from general academic anxiety. They highlighted communication apprehension, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation as the primary components of FLCA. These elements form the basis of FLCA and are particularly relevant in the context of language learning, where students must regularly perform and be evaluated in the target language. Delving further into this, MacIntyre & Gardner (1994) showed how anxiety disrupts cognitive functioning such as memory and information processing, especially during

crucial stages of vocabulary acquisition. Their study, designed to show that anxiety impedes the acquisition of vocabulary, brought out the cognitive dimension of FLCA and the related effects on important learning processes.

Therefore, this is what actually prompted my research study since research participants on my study can be challenged with the target language especially when they perform in class. Repeatedly, it has been documented that learners with low self-perceived speaking ability do have higher levels of anxiety particularly if they are threatened to be evaluated negatively. For example, Al-Khotaba et al. (2019) assessed Saudi EFL learners' speaking anxiety and noticed that the high level of speaking anxiety influenced their performance due to the fear of error commitment in speaking tasks. This was consistent with the more general view that performance and evaluation-oriented anxiety is a core factor in FLCA. Likewise, Gregersen & Horwitz (2002) related FLCA to perfectionism, showing that anxious learners usually set unrealistically high standard and are afraid of errors, which makes the level of anxiety increase and lowers the level of participation.

They discovered that these learners are hypercritical of their own performance and incredibly anxious about making mistakes, which greatly magnifies the level of anxiety. Among these factors, Dewaele & Li (2022) highlight self-perceived competence as the one that will have a strong influence on both positive and negative emotional experiences related to language learning. Their research shows that self-reported speaking and grammar competence significantly predicts FLCA and FLE; that is, learners who think they are more competent in some language domains show less anxiety and higher enjoyment. Hence, the higher or lower self-perceived speaking abilities among Thai postgraduate students can be related to the results of the current research based on studies previously done.

By taking a more qualitative approach, the contribution of personality, especially in the context of foreign language anxiety, will be considered. Botes et al. (2023) examined the relationship between personality and FLCA, and they discovered a strong relation between neuroticism (which is associated with emotional instability, nervousness, irritability, sadness, and anxiety) and higher levels of anxiety.

In fact, their study revealed the fact that students who have high levels of neuroticism are more likely to face FLCA, a fact that leads to the assumption that emotional instability has an essential contribution to the appearance of language learning anxiety. In the study conducted by Gregersen & Horwitz 2002, it has been proved that anxious language learners commonly demonstrate perfectionist characteristics such as higher personal performance standards, fear of evaluation, and greater procrastination. However, the oral performance lessons become intensified under these standards, fear, and features.

In the same line, Kitano (2001) reported that fear of negative evaluation and perceived speaking competence are the major contributing factors to FLCA among college learners of Japanese. The implication of the two studies is that since the identified sources of anxiety had been established earlier on, educators need to address them in a bid to improve language learning. Educators should design supportive classroom contexts that reduce perceptions of making mistakes and enhance realistic self-appraisal.

Jiang & Dewaele (2019) further elaborated the role of cultural and situational factors in relation to FLCA, putting in view that educational and cultural contexts significantly affect anxiety levels among Chinese EFL learners. They have found that it is one's cultural background and learning environment that shapes beliefs and attitudes toward language learning, thus influencing anxiety levels. In the same line of argument, Horwitz (1999) and Dewaele & Ip (2013) also accentuated the role of culture in FLCA. Learners' attitudes and feelings, or FLCA,

are determined by their belief regarding language learning, and this is heavily impacted by their own cultural background. A case in point is the difference between American learners with that of Korean or Turkish heritage learners in the belief about language learning, thus their approach to language learning and the anxiety also differs. This depicts the need for educators to incorporate cultural settings while formulating methods to handle FLCA.

For example, research by Dewey, Belnap, and Steffen (2018) also evidenced the influence of studying abroad on the level of FLCA. It showed that, despite time passing by and shifting into a stage with decreased classroom anxiety and more enjoyment, this decrease in negative emotions can only be viewed as a reduction of some parameters from student physiological measures; thus, the overall FLCA remains at sufficiently high levels attributed to the stressors related to study abroad. The present study took into consideration the cultural factor that pertains to Asian cultures and Thai cultures. Being international students, FLCA may yield not only the learning outcomes of the participants but also their speaking abilities.

Research on the remote learning environments in the last pandemic crisis provided deeper insight into FLCA and furnished information on learners in a foreign language. This newly experienced shift in education due to COVID-19 helps identify that FLCA is indeed dynamic. It was found by Dewaele, Albakistani, and Ahmed (2024) that there were significant differences in FLCA, FLE, and FLB (Foreign Language Boredom) between in-person and emergency remote teaching (ERT) settings. The authors described that FLCA tended to be higher in face-to-face settings because of the dynamics between people and interactional pressure. On the other hand, ERT added its own constraints, such as internet connectivity problems and the impersonality of online communication, which impacted individual students differently.

In the similar vein, the research by Bashori et al. (2022) was on web-based language learning, through which this study aimed to find the relationship between speaking anxiety of Indonesian vocational high school students and how web-based platforms implementing ASR technology, such as Automatic Speech Recognition, reduce the fear to speak by creating a less intimidating environment for them to practice — a technology feature in alleviating FLCA.

Learners' emotions have effects on learning, so they may make it or break classroom settings. MacIntyre & Gregersen (2012) looked at the way in which positive affect, such as enjoyment, would have a mitigating effect on the negative nature of anxiety. They found that a more positive emotional classroom climate increased motivation and involvement, thus moderating the negative effects of FLCA. Dewaele et al. (2019) investigated the FLCA-FLE link among Kazakh learners of Turkish and found it to be weakly positively correlated. This indicates that although these emotions are distinct, they would coexist and interact in complex ways. The study identified the learning context, constructed through teacher behavior, as important in developing and framing students' emotions.

Moreover, Tsang & Dewaele (2023) investigated young EFL learners from Hong Kong and discovered that in the case of these subjects, FLCA and FLB predicted lower engagement and proficiency levels while FLE was positively correlated. They proposed that an interesting, supportive learning environment is important for boosting educational outcomes. The significant effect of these emotions on learning and performance is pointed out by the research body of FLE, FLCA, and FLB in the FL learners. Dewaele, Botes and Greiff (2023) probed sources and effects of these emotions and found that teacher behaviors - the frequency of foreign language use in class and unpredictability - are important sources of variation for FLE, not for FLCA. Perhaps other forces impinge on these emotions. That said, Dewaele and Saito (2024) broadened this research on the affective dimension of learning the English language and

Languages Other than English (LOTE) to establish that the degrees to which learners are affected by FLCA while learning LOTEs are much different from those learning the English language. This showed that different contexts required different strategies.

Overall, the research on FLCA highlights the complex interplay of personal, situational, and cultural factors in shaping language learners' emotional experiences. Effective strategies to mitigate FLCA include creating supportive classroom environments, leveraging technology, and understanding the specific needs and backgrounds of learners.

2.4.2 Studies FLE

The considerable amount of research into Foreign Language Enjoyment underlines the importance of this factor for language learning and gives notice of how it can foster higher student motivation, involvement, and success. According to Dewaele, FLE is very much related to cognitive, affective, and social aspects that jointly facilitate the process of acquiring a second language. This is because of the excitement and feeling of achievement that one acquires when it is possible to learn a new language and communicate properly in the end. In addition, a good social climate within the class may help reduce some of the stress and anxiety elicited from learning a language.

Dewaele's research has demonstrated that FLE positively affects learner attitudes and behaviors by encouraging participation, linguistic risk-taking, and perseverance in language learning—all of which are significantly associated with higher linguistic competence and improved performance in language courses (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2016). He also found that educators are highly recommended to employ techniques that generate pleasure, such as interactive games and activities, and the use of attractive authentic materials. Promoting positive social interaction further enhances FLE, contributing to a supportive and inclusive classroom

environment that boosts learning outcomes (Dewaele, 2019). FLE serves as a robust protective factor against academic challenges, safeguarding students from anxiety and boredom associated with school activities. This evidence suggests that educational practice should strive for a balance between cognitive-linguistic and emotional well-being (Dewaele, 2024).

It goes without saying that teacher behaviors and the physical environment of the classroom are also very important in fostering FLE. Myhre et al. (2023) found teacher behaviors, such as predictability, frequency of using the foreign language in class, and humor, positively correlate with FLE and motivation. However, these behaviors did not significantly reduce FLCA, indicating that anxiety may be influenced by factors beyond teacher behavior. This study illuminates how teacher behaviors can enhance student enjoyment and motivation, suggesting that supportive and engaging teacher practices are important in creating positive learning environments.

Similarly, Dewaele and colleagues explored how specific variables related to teacher interaction impact the emotional experience of Spanish learners of English. They discovered a weak to moderate negative relationship of 20% between FLE and FLCA, which is due to the presence of positive teacher characteristics such as being friendly. It is noted that these characteristics are directly associated with enhancing FLE and negatively correlated with reducing FLCA, thereby pointing to the fact that the variance in teacher behaviors may promote one variable at the expense of another – anxiety as opposed to enjoyment (Dewaele, Magdalena, & Saito, 2019).

The findings of these studies support Nemati et al.'s (2020) study that underlines teacher encouragement, innovation in teaching methods, and the presence of a positive classroom atmosphere to increase FLE among Iranian EFL learners. But, while strongly advocating the

use of enjoyable activities, these studies also suggest that enjoyment in itself is not sufficient; the quality and nature of the activities are important in order to gain maximum benefit.

The classroom environment, whether remote or physical, is an imperative predictor of FLE. Existing empirical investigations propound that higher levels of FLE are mostly discovered in traditional classrooms where direct and active teacher involvement is high; on the other hand, the remote atmosphere is characterized by a sense of isolation that could lead to diminished FLE and higher levels of anxiety and boredom (Li & Wei, 2022). Moreover, Myhre et al. (2023) researched outdoor educational settings that are generally less formal and more active to determine whether they result in a decrease in Foreign Language Anxiety (FLA) and an increase in FLE among young adolescents. Although the qualitative data showed only slight differences in the measured FLA and FLE, it proposed strong emotional benefits derived from outdoor learning, noting the potential of alternative educational settings for enhancing language learning experiences.

Exploring the cultural dimensions of these emotional constructs, Jiang et al. (2019) analysed FLCA and FLE in a sample of Chinese EFL learners compared to an international sample. Their mixed-methods study indicated that, although the emotional experiences of Chinese learners were different, the underlying dynamics were still similar to global trends: FLE was predicted more significantly by teacher-related factors, while FLCA was strongly connected with learner-internal variables such as fear of negative evaluation (Jiang & Dewaele, 2019). In a different cultural context, using Kazakh learners of Turkish, Dewaele et al. (2019) found attitudes towards the Turkish language and teacher-related factors to significantly predict both FLE and FLCA. Positive attitudes and supportive teacher behavior were shown not only to enhance enjoyment but also to moderate anxiety, showing that these emotional states, while related, are influenced by a separate set of factors (Dewaele et al., 2019).

Dewaele & MacIntyre (2019) delved deeper into the role of multicultural personality traits and other learner and teacher variables. Their research provided support for the hypothesis that, while the dimensions are often seen as two sides of a coin, FLE and FLCA are not inversely related constructs but separate and interrelated. They found that personality traits are more predictive of FLCA than for FLE, meaning individual psychological profiles play a greater role in anxiety than enjoyment. The latter seems to depend more on environmental and interactive factors, rather than the inner self. Further studies have emphasized the significant role of emotional intelligence (EI) in promoting FLE and language learning achievement, with high EI strongly correlated with enhanced FLE and better language performance, highlighting the importance of emotional competencies in educational environments (Li, 2020).

These are all empirical studies, which demonstrate the great complexity of the emotional landscape in foreign language learning, underlining the strong influence of the contextual, interpersonal, and individual variables on the learners' emotional experiences. Insight into the interdependence of these factors must be obtained as educators and policymakers try to better the environment for language learning.

2.4.3 Foreign Language Anxiety and Enjoyment in Speaking

With the conclusion of the research, empirical studies on FLE and FLCA, the present research is bound to elaborate further on speaking skills in a foreign language. This will provide the current study with more elaborated and strong ideas, considered important in the context of Thai TESOL postgraduate students studying in the UK.

The collection of studies on English as a Foreign Language (EFL) speaking anxiety offers a comprehensive view of the various dimensions and impacts of this phenomenon. In agreement with Horwitz, Tallon, and Luo (2010), it is very clear that speaking anxiety constitutes a major

emotional stumbling block to learning the language. This anxiety is related to the fear of negative evaluation, unpreparedness, and general speaking class anxiety, these are the key inhibitors that limit considerably learners' ability to perform and engage in language activity (Batiha et al., 2016). For example, findings highly relate to those by Muhammad (2019) and Burns (2019), who discuss the importance of effective communication skills in English more than the other language skills.

However, weaknesses and diverging points can also be drawn from these studies. For instance, while Batiha et al. (2016) registered no significant difference in gender among speaking anxiety factors, Mahmoodzadeh (2012) found that female learners in Iran showed higher levels of anxiety than males. This inconsistency may suggest that cultural and contextual issues are more contributory to speaking anxiety than gender alone. This does show that a more nuanced, context-specific study is essential.

Moreover, these studies use diverse methodologies, which means that their findings are hardly generalisable. The mix-methods research by Rumiya & Seftika (2018) gave a robust analysis through both qualitative and quantitative data. However, their focus on a single institution limits the applicability of their conclusions. The survey on Thai students in Indonesia, conducted by Syifa Lum'atuddina & Miftachudin (2021), is also worth considering, although the study is more limited with respect to the number of participants.

The studies emphasize the two main causes of speaking anxiety, which have been linked with the fear of negative evaluation and lack of vocabulary. This is most notable in the case of Roihan Chema & Soviyah's research (2022), whereby the fear of making mistakes and being judged by the peers significantly limited students from participation. This agreed with

Horwitz et al. (1986) who found out anxiety is shown in stuttering, freezing, and speeding up speech, reducing performance and practice chances.

Furthermore, results on the impacts of speaking anxiety on academic performances and wellbeing are quite startling. Phormphithak (2023) stresses that it negatively affects cognitive functions and physical health, which in effect lead to low participation and hence a poor learning experience. This, as suggested by Phormphithak, calls for the use of supportive pedagogical strategy in creating a low anxiety learning environment that will encourage voluntary participation, with positive feedback.

On the other hand, the concept of foreign language enjoyment (FLE) has recently been recognized as a significant positive emotion affecting enjoyment in speaking. Dewaele & MacIntyre (2019) argue that FLE is crucial for fostering successful communication and overcoming linguistic barriers, which broadens learners' focus, enhances resilience, and maintains a favourable attitude towards language learning challenges. This view is well attested in the literature, which also supports a strong positive effect of enjoyment on language learning. But, of course, the extent to which FLE can counterbalance anxiety and improve the level of speaking performance will be different for each learner, because individual emotional experience is one of the pivotal factors in language learning.

MacIntyre & Dewaele (2014) further this point by highlighting a number of specific activities in the classroom that promote FLE: role plays, debates, and group presentations. They found that FLE was negatively significantly correlated with Foreign Language Anxiety ($r = -0.36$); this means that lower levels of anxiety can associate with greater enjoyment in language classes. This relationship, therefore, has important implications for how FLE might reduce anxiety and enhance speaking confidence. However, the meta-analysis provides a much

broader perspective, with strong positive correlations of FLE with Willingness to Communicate (WTC) ($r = 0.48$), academic achievement ($r = 0.30$), and self-perceived achievement ($r = 0.27$) (Botes et al., 2022). Although these findings do suggest the beneficial effects of FLE, they also point to the necessity of more fine-grained research into the manner in which various factors interplay in realizing effective language learning outcomes.

Research by Dicer (2017) and Thumvichit (2022), that positive emotions can enhance language learning experiences. According to Dicer (2017), the identification of the fact that it is enjoyable to be able to speak English will allow teachers to design more engaging tasks. In the views of Thumvichit (2022), speaking and interaction in activities are central to classroom engagement, and enjoyment is significantly correlated to speaking task engagement.

The reviewed research studies reveal the complicated relationship between FLCA and foreign FLE in the speaking contexts of EFL. Anxiety is a key obstacle to achieving competence in learning a second language, while enjoyment can become one of the factors that offset this negative influence and increase the effectiveness of learning. Both the emotional factors influenced by the experiences of the individuals and the cultural context have an important implication on the quality of educational methodologies. These insights provide an understanding of the emotional dynamics lived by Thai TESOL postgraduate students. These insights relate directly to your research on speaking anxiety and enjoyment in this group.

2.5 Research Questions

The research clearly shows that speaking anxiety in foreign languages, in particular, is a global problem that has a detrimental effect on students everywhere. Several studies have demonstrated how nervousness can seriously impair students' ability to communicate in English, causing them to become confused or freeze during speech, disrupt conversations, and become less eager to communicate. This can have a significant negative impact on students' learning experiences and decrease their level of interest in class for those taking university courses and foreign language classes when English is the primary communication language. Due to their difficulties speaking English and their fear of making mistakes and embarrassing themselves, students may feel anxious during class discussions and activities instead of actively engaging.

Furthermore, the majority of empirical study on speaking anxiety has concentrated on five main areas: the causes of anxiety, the effects of anxiety, the degree of speaking anxiety among students, and the attitudes of students. This includes studies conducted in the Thai setting. In order to better comprehend the problem via the experiences and perspectives of international students, three study questions were created based on these themes.

In particular, these research questions focus on Thai postgraduate TESOL learners in the UK address areas that needs more concrete investigation (Chinpakdee, 2015; Bhattarachaiyakorn & Phettakua, 2023). With a focus on speaking abilities in particular, this section examines the broad profiles and correlations between FLCA and FLE. Emotional experiences in language learning situations are greatly influenced by the particular problems that these learners

encounter, such as language limitations and cultural adaptation. This research attempts to offer comprehensive insights into the speaking anxiety and delight experienced by these learners by looking at the origins of FLCA and FLE.

The unique emotional experiences of Thai postgraduate TESOL learners in the UK are still not widely recognised, despite a number of studies on FLCA and FLE. Studies on language acquisition anxiety and satisfaction in general are mostly available, but they frequently overlook the particular context of speaking abilities among Thai international students. Furthermore, there is not much information about the influence of these emotions on learners' speaking abilities because the interaction between FLCA and FLE in this demographic has not been fully investigated. By filling in these inconsistencies, this study attempts to improve our knowledge of FLCA and FLE by offering a thorough examination of the ways in which speaking anxiety and enjoyment interact and affect Thai postgraduate TESOL students' learning experiences in the UK. This greater knowledge could guide the development of more effective teaching techniques that foster a classroom climate that is encouraging and low anxiety, thereby enhancing student performance and engagement in language learning.

Based on the existing literature and to address the gap, the following research questions were explored in this study:

1. What are the general profiles of FLCA and FLE specifically in relation to speaking skills among Thai postgraduate TESOL learners based in the UK?
2. What are the relationships between FLCA and FLE with a specific focus on speaking skills among these individuals?
3. According to the learners, what are the sources of FLCA and FLE when it comes to speaking skills?

2.6 Conclusion

Thus, the study of Thai TESOL postgraduate students in the UK presents a crucial attempt to explore the issues they face regarding cultural adaptation, language barriers, and the pressures of postgraduate study. Therefore, this research serves as an important addition to the underdeveloped literature on the levels of FLCA and FLE of the students. Knowing about these emotional experiences will help us understand the ways these factors have impacts on their learning outcomes and general success.

The findings of this research, therefore, will contribute towards more detailed understanding of the emotional contexts of Thai TESOL postgraduate learners within the UK. It helps educators design more targeted and supportive teaching strategies with clear identification of the specific triggers of anxiety and sources of enjoyment. This will help reduce anxiety and create a more positive and engaging learning environment. Further, such research would offer some practical pedagogical implication, thereby providing guidelines for educators regarding emotional and academic support to be able to better serve the students.

Ultimately, this study seeks to enhance the learning experience and outcomes of Thai TESOL postgraduate students in the UK with the belief that they will be better prepared for success in their studies and future teaching careers.

3. Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The study examined the effects of FLCA and FLE on the speaking skills of Thai TESOL postgraduates in the UK using a mixed-method approach. It employed standardized scales for quantitative data and semi-structured interviews for qualitative insights. However, with only 14 participants, the study faced limitations in generalizability and statistical power, potentially affecting the robustness of conclusions drawn from such a small sample.

Data were analysed using statistical methods for questionnaires and thematic analysis for interviews, aiming to uncover the intricate relationships between emotions and language learning. Ethical considerations, including informed consent and participant anonymity, were rigorously maintained to ensure the integrity of the research process. Despite its small scale, the study sought to contribute valuable insights into how emotions impact language learning, which could inform future teaching strategies in TESOL programs.

3.2 Mixed-methods Research

In this mixed-methods study, two questionnaires, the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) and the Foreign Language Enjoyment Scale (FLES), were used alongside semi-structured interviews to examine language learners' emotions. The questionnaires quantified students' anxiety and enjoyment, while the interviews provided deeper insights into their personal experiences, enriching the understanding of how these emotions impact their language learning.

3.3 Participants

The study involved 14 Thai postgraduates studying in the TESOL program at various universities in the United Kingdom, comprising two males and twelve females, resulting in a gender distribution of approximately 14% males and 86% females. These participants were selected based on their enrolment in TESOL programs and their native Thai language background.

Recruitment was conducted through snowball sampling, utilizing social media and professional networks pertinent to Thai postgraduates in the UK. Specifically, the researcher contacted Thai TESOL postgraduate students through online platforms such as the Line application, Facebook groups, and Facebook Messenger. The recruitment process lasted 20 days, from 1st May to 20th May. Participants were provided with detailed information sheets (see Appendix 7) and consent forms (see Appendix 8) electronically, emphasizing the voluntary nature of the study and their right to withdraw at any point without consequence.

All participants had IELTS scores above 6.5, indicating their proficiency in English. They were given the autonomy to decide whether to take part in the research or not. Most of the participants started their studies at UK universities in late September 2023 for a one-year program. Only two participants completed their master's degrees over two years ago.

Their classes were conducted in English, predominantly through seminar-based onsite sessions. Seven out of the 14 participants, equivalent to 50%, were selected for interviews based on their high scores on FLCA and FLE and their willingness to be interviewed. It is important to note that only female participants were interviewed. Although the two male participants had some of the highest scores in FLCA and FLE, they were not willing to participate in the interviews. For privacy concerns, all interviewees were free to turn off their cameras during the interview.

Figure 1: Mixed-methods Research

3.4 Instrument

In the current study, two questionnaires were employed without adjustment: the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) (see Appendix 3) and the Foreign Language Enjoyment Scale (FLES) (see Appendix 4). These scales were not created by the researcher but were used to maintain the original content and ensure the reliable results of the research. Both FLCAS and FLES questionnaires were administered using Google Forms. Additionally, based on a mixed-method approach, online interviews were conducted with questions designed and inspired by Dörnyei (2005).

3.4.1 Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale

The Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), developed by Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986), is a widely used instrument designed to measure the specific anxiety experienced in the foreign language learning environment. Comprising 33 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree," the FLCAS addresses various anxiety aspects such as fear of speaking, fear of negative evaluation, and communication apprehension. Statements like "I never feel quite sure of myself when I am speaking in my foreign language class." and "I tremble when I know that I'm going to be called on in language class." help identify anxiety triggers.

Previous research validates the FLCAS with a high reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha of .902), indicating internal consistency (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2018). The total score ranges from 33 to 165, with scores over 72 indicating high anxiety, scores between 54 and 72 indicating moderate anxiety, and scores below 54 indicating low anxiety. The items focus on three primary domains: Test anxiety, which measures stress related to language assessments and fear of performing poorly; Fear of Negative Evaluation, which concerns being negatively judged based on language proficiency; and Communication apprehension, which examines the

unease of speaking or performing in a foreign language in front of others. By assessing responses to these statements, teachers can pinpoint particular anxiety triggers in their learners, facilitating targeted support and intervention.

3.4.2 Foreign Language Enjoyment Scale

This study also utilized the Foreign Language Enjoyment Scale (FLES), developed by Botes, Dewaele, MacIntyre, and Greiff in 2019, to measure enjoyment levels among participants in foreign language classes. The FLES comprises 21 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree." The items assess various aspects of enjoyment experienced in the foreign language classroom, such as creativity, positive emotions, and a supportive environment. Participants responded to statements like "I can be creative." and "I enjoy it." The total score on the FLES ranges from 21 to 105, with higher scores indicating greater enjoyment. Previous research has validated the FLES, with a reported reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) of .902, indicating high internal consistency. This scale has been employed in studies by Li (2019), Dewaele & MacIntyre (2018), and MacIntyre & Mercer (2014), among others.

3.4.3 Interview

In this study, semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore three key topics: General Profiles of FLCA and FLE, Relationships between FLE and FLCA in Speaking Skills, and Sources of FLE and FLCA in Speaking Skills. These interviews involved a set of guiding questions and prompts prepared in advance but allowed for open-ended responses. This format enables the interviewer to steer the conversation while giving the interviewee the opportunity to elaborate on their thoughts and feelings (Dörnyei, 2005). The interview questions (see Appendix 5) were divided into two parts: ice-breaking questions aimed at making the

participants comfortable and allowing them to introduce themselves, such as "Why did you choose to study TESOL in the UK?" The main questions, inspired by Dörnyei's work (2005), were designed to explore participants' emotional experiences in the classroom, aiming to uncover the reasons behind different emotions experienced during language learning. The interviews typically lasted around 15 minutes, allowing for a detailed exploration of the participants' emotional responses and the factors influencing them. Some of the interview questions included:

General Profiles of FLCA and FLE

- How do your background and previous experiences influence your feelings of anxiety or enjoyment when speaking in a foreign language?

Relationships between FLE and FLCA in Speaking Skills

- Can you describe specific instances where you felt particularly anxious or enjoyed speaking in a foreign language during class?
- How do these experiences relate to your performance or participation in speaking activities?

Sources of FLE and FLCA in Speaking Skills

- What strategies do you use to manage feelings of anxiety or enjoyment to improve your speaking skills?
- What do you think are the main factors that contribute to your feelings of enjoyment when speaking a foreign language in class?

3.5 Data Collection

Quantitative data collection, lasting 31 days, commenced on 17th May 2024 through the administration of online questionnaires, which continued until 16th June 2024.

The initial phase involved the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) and the Foreign Language Enjoyment Scale (FLES), both administered via Google Forms. Participants were required to read a detailed consent form before beginning the questionnaires. This form, which took approximately 10 minutes to read, outlined the study's objectives, the rationale for participant selection, the procedures involved, and ethical considerations such as confidentiality and voluntary participation. Participants who agreed to take part signed two copies of the consent form—one for their records and one to be returned to the researcher. Completing the FLCAS and FLES questionnaires took about 15 minutes. Responses were automatically collected and securely stored in the researcher's Google account, and participants received a copy of their responses via email. After collecting the quantitative data, initial analysis was performed to calculate the FLCA and FLE scores for each participant. The top 7 participants with the highest levels of anxiety and enjoyment were identified and invited to participate in follow-up interviews, ensuring representation of a range of emotional experiences.

Qualitative data collection took 17 days, from 27th May 2024 to 12th June 2024, focusing on personal experiences and emotional responses related to foreign language learning. These in-depth interviews were conducted via Zoom, allowing for flexibility and convenience for participants. Before the interviews, participants were briefed on the study's purpose and their rights, including confidentiality and the option to withdraw at any time.

The interviews began with two ice-breaking questions to put participants at ease, followed by ten main questions designed to delve into their experiences with foreign language anxiety and

enjoyment. Topics covered included their background and previous experiences, specific instances of anxiety or enjoyment, strategies for managing these emotions, and factors contributing to their emotional responses during language learning. Each interview lasted between 15 to 20 minutes and was recorded with participants' consent, with recordings securely stored in the Zoom UCL cloud for analysis. Seven participants completed the interviews, providing rich qualitative data to complement the quantitative findings. This mixed-methods approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of the participants' emotional experiences in foreign language learning, integrating both broad-scale quantitative insights and detailed qualitative narratives.

Figure 2: Data Collection

3.6 Data Analysis

In this research, I utilized the FLCAS to quantify the levels of anxiety among Thai postgraduate TESOL learners. This scale helps in identifying specific aspects of speaking anxiety, such as apprehension about speaking in front of others, fear of making grammatical mistakes, or anxiety over not being understood. In addition, I used the FLES to assess the levels of enjoyment learners experience while engaging in speaking activities. This could include enjoyment derived from successful communication, the challenge of expressing complex ideas, or social interactions in the classroom. All the questionnaires of the data were first entered into Excel and then analysed through Google Sheets.

I primarily utilized open coding and constant comparison methods for data analysis, aiming to generalize relevant issues and uncover the pedagogical implications from the collected data. Initially, the recorded interviews were transcribed via Zoom utility and edited. The translated transcripts were thoroughly reviewed for coding. During this process, I engaged in a detailed analysis of the interview transcripts and my field notes to code as extensively as possible. Once the interviews were done, I used the Interview Transcription Key (see Appendix 1) for transcription, noting pauses less than 3 seconds as (...), pauses more than 3 seconds as (.....), laughs as (LF), and fillers such as Em/Uh. Moreover, I used the coding scheme of interviews (see Appendix 1) to analyse the qualitative data from the interviews based on Sala et al. (2008). The categories identified through open coding were continuously refined and compared with one another to enhance the richness of information and the relationships within and across these categories. Throughout the coding process, I frequently revisited the original video recordings and transcripts to ensure the accuracy of the translations and to further saturate the categories and their properties. Additionally, I reached out to some of the interviewed participants to clarify their responses during the data analysis phase.

For research question 1, I explored the common patterns of anxiety and enjoyment among Thai TESOL postgraduate students, identifying specific triggers for anxiety such as fear of making mistakes and peer judgment, alongside sources of enjoyment like successful communication and positive feedback. Additionally, I examined how anxiety impacts their speaking abilities in classroom settings, utilizing data derived from both statistical analysis and interview results to provide a comprehensive overview.

For research question 2, I employed qualitative analysis to delve into how various factors influence speaking experiences among these students. This includes examining how confidence, anxiety, teaching methods, peer interactions, and classroom dynamics affect their ability to speak. The coding scheme outlined in the appendix, which details these specific aspects, guiding the analysis, ensuring that each element is thoroughly evaluated in relation to speaking skills.

For research question 3, I synthesized the findings from the quantitative questionnaire results with insights from the qualitative interviews. This integration helped bridge any unexplored areas between empirical data and personal experiences reported by the students, offering a well-rounded answer to how both sets of data correlated and what this implied for their speaking skills and overall language learning experience.

3.7 Ethics

This study adhered to the strict guidelines of the ethical committee. The concerned institutional review board was approached for prior ethical approval before the commencement of data collection (see Appendix 6). All the participants in this study were volunteers and informed well in advance about the background of the research and their rights. According to the

information statement and consent form given to the participants, they could withdraw from the study without stating a reason at any given time. In the first place, to ensure complete anonymity, the participants were assigned a number (from Participant 1 to Participant 14) in place of their name. Any other personal information for the identification of the participant had been removed carefully. No personal data regarding the participants was disclosed to third parties and it was only used for academic purposes within this study, shared only between the main researcher and the dissertation supervisor.

The interviews were ensured to highlight the participants' comfort in the exchange and their readiness to share information regarding their experiences to be created in a supportive and non-threatening atmosphere. They were also provided that personal information will remain confidential and true emotions could be shared while completing the questionnaire, not feeling nervous, uncomfortable, or embarrassed. Only data fully reflecting their true emotional experience in the foreign language class matters. They were offered video recording during interviews, only if the participants wanted that. Two of the participants preferred that they not video record. They were also asked whether they would wish to continue in case they felt uncomfortable or embarrassed in any manner, with the absolute freedom to respond. If they decided to withdraw, they could do so freely without giving reasons, and their data would be deleted from the study.

All the research data were safely stored following the Information Security Management Policy of the IOE. Data in digital form were stored in a password-protected system with access granted to the researcher only. Hard copy data were stored digitally in an external hard drive. The anonymity and confidentiality of all the participants were guaranteed, and the data were used for this research alone.

4. Findings

4.1 Quantitative data

Initially, descriptive analysis was conducted in Google Sheets with the data collected from the two questionnaires.

FLCA Analysis

Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	2.74	1.24
2	2.74	1.29
3	2.58	1.12
4	1.61	1.15
5	2.52	1.69
6	2.42	1.09
7	2.58	1.20
8	2.52	1.09
9	2.90	1.04
10	2.29	1.22
11	2.35	1.31
12	2.77	0.80
13	2.00	1.24
14	2.10	1.40

Table 1: FLCAS Analysis

The following table represents the anxiety scores of 14 participants of a study that utilized the FLCAS. The findings were diverse, with mean anxiety scores that spread between 1.61 and 2.90, as well as fluctuations in how consistently each participant experienced the feeling of anxiety, which can be observed by looking at the standard deviations that ranged from 0.80 to 1.69.

On the other hand, Participant 9 obtained the highest average rating for anxiousness: 2.90; however, her results had a lower variation among the participants, showing a standard deviation of just 1.04. Meanwhile, Participant 4 scored lowest for anxiousness at 1.61, yet still with a moderate level of inconsistency at a standard deviation of 1.15. Participant 12 had a high mean of 2.77 compared to the other participants, and showed the least variation in feelings, with the lowest standard deviation of 0.80.

On average, the anxiety levels are moderate, with several participants yielding mean scores around 2.50 and standard deviations around 1.10. Data present evidence of a medium level of anxiety among participants; the highest levels are significantly higher compared to the lowest but with some variability as indicated by the standard deviations.

FLE Analysis

Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	4.10	0.70
2	3.00	0.77
3	4.10	0.44
4	4.76	0.89
5	4.57	0.68
6	4.24	0.94
7	4.38	0.86
8	4.71	0.46
9	4.38	0.74
10	3.52	1.08
11	4.43	0.68
12	3.29	0.85
13	4.05	0.67
14	4.57	1.03

Table 2: FLES Analysis

As indicated by Table 2, the 14 participants took the FLES. The range of mean scores by participants ranges between 3.00 and 4.76, while standard deviations vary in the range of 0.44 to 1.08. Again, this underscores varying levels of enjoyment among participants.

Participant 4 obtained the highest mean enjoyment level of 4.76 with a standard deviation of 0.89. Participant 3 reported a mean enjoyment level at 4.10, with the lowest standard deviation of 0.44. Participant 2 reported the lowest mean enjoyment level at 3.00, with a standard deviation of 0.77.

Most of the mean scores lie around 4.30 on average, while most of the standard deviations lie around 0.70. It shows that in general, they found the activities highly enjoyable—ranging from significantly higher scores at the top end to much lower scores at the bottom end of the scale—with some variability indicated by the standard deviations.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
age	14	17	29	46	31.36	4.41
anxiety	14	40	50	90	75.57	10.83
enjoyment	14	31	69	100	87.70	17.04

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

This table illustrates that participants in this research are 14 individuals and different descriptive statistics are expressed for age, anxiety, and enjoyment. The participants are between 29 and 46 years old, with the mean age being 31.36 years and the standard deviation 4.41. This means that participants in this study are relatively close in age, with the majority having their early 30s.

The anxiety scores range from 50 to 90, with the mean score at 75.57 and the standard deviation at 10.83, which allows us to conclude about moderate levels of anxiety, as a few people show higher amounts of anxiety than the rest.

On the other hand, the levels of enjoyment according to the FLE questionnaire range from 69 to 100, with a mean score of 87.70 and a standard deviation of 17.04. This demonstrates a relatively high enjoyment level, although there is large dispersion among the participants.

Participant Age

Figure 3: Participant Age

According to Diagram 3, the participants in the study are distributed across various age groups. Most of the participants are 31 years old, accounting for 42.9% of the sample. The second largest participants, who make up 28.6% of the sample, are aged 30. The remaining age groups, each representing 7.1% of the sample, include participants aged 29, 32, 33, and 46. This indicates that some age diversity is marked with a significant portion located within the early 30s of age, particularly around 31 years old.

4.2 Qualitative data

4.2.1 Sources of FLCA

Category	FLCA-self	FLCA-teacher	FLCA-peers
Source	conducting a presentation (3); speak in foreign language (3); being judged by others (3), fear of making mistakes (2); lacking of preparation (2); lacking of some background knowledge (1)	experience a negative teaching style (3)	attending in a big class (2)
In total	14	3	2

Table 4: Three Categories of FLCA and the Number of Tokens

It can be evidenced from Table 4 that the sources of FLCA have been significantly categorised into three: FLCA-self, FLCA-teacher, and FLCA-peers. Each category has certain subcategories with regard to the sources of reported anxiety by the participants. Among the three categories, the most affected sources of FLCA belong to the FLCA-self with 14 tokens, and teacher-related and peer-related factors occupied the next level of positions.

The category FLCA-teacher illustrates the anxiety emerging during the interaction with the teacher. For instance, participants addressed that a negative teaching style is the cause for their anxiousness (3) and there were 3 token occurrences in this type.

The FLCA-peers category deals with anxiousness fears concerning peers. Participants said that going to a big class leads to such an experience (2) in this type. There were 2 token occurrences in this type.

FLCA-self

Conducting a Presentation

The individuals themselves are one of the most significant causes of anxiety in the foreign language classroom. Among the three interviewees, Participants 2, 3, and 7 rated giving a presentation in the classroom context in front of classmates as either their highest point of anxiety or pressure, as it strongly impeded their performance.

Interviewee 2: p. 4, line 35 - 38

“The most, and like anxious moment would be like (...) to make an individual presentation. Yeah, because I did this like 2 or 3 weeks ago that I had to present about my presentation, and like to share, which is like I was so excited, is like, really nervous.”

Speak in Foreign Language

As indicated as one of the most sources of FLCA, Participants 1, 4, and 6 mentioned this problem. Participant 1 commented that she felt excited and, at the same time, nervous when she was speaking in a foreign language in class. Participant 2 related her fear to speaking English, especially not being prepared enough. There is much fear about fluency and errors. Participant 3 gave an example of how she felt anxious when she first came to a new country and had no idea about their classmates' level of proficiency in English. This kind of uncertainty about the skill level contributed to anxious feelings.

Interviewee 1: p. 2, line 38 - 39

“These experiences directly affect my performance. When I'm anxious, I tend to speak less and hesitate more which can hinder my participation.”

Being Judged by Others and Fear of Making Mistakes

In similar vein, the fear of being judged by peers and of making mistakes were also the major anxiety-provoking triggers among participants 1, 3, and 7. Participants 1 and 3 said that nervousness mainly happens when there is a big opportunity to make mistakes or to be judged by their peers. Such conditions were an overall happening that affected them in being responsive during class discussions and class activities. Participant 7 concurred with this and expressed a worry about making mistakes and being judged by classmates or teachers. This made her unconfident, participate less in speaking activities, and always worry about being negatively judged.

Interviewee 7: p. 21, line 8 - 11

“I feel like I was worried about making mistake and being judged by my classmates, all my teachers. (...) and I feel like this fear often made me feel hesitate to participate in the speaking activities in the classroom.”

Lacking of Preparation

Some of the participants, especially Participant 3 and Participant 6, clearly indicated the associated issues such as inadequate preparation and inadequate background knowledge, which led to some of their anxiety. The anxiety was best described by Participant 3 regarding when she attended a class without preparing in advance: failure to read or deliberate self-causing of being unready to share on the material caused her quite some anxiety. Likewise, Participant 6 elaborated that, in general, the lack of background knowledge attributed to the level of her anxiety. They explained how not understanding a subject right from its basics only increased anxiety, most especially when they would be called upon to discuss a very complex or abstract subject.

Interviewee 6: p. 18, line 26 - 28

“I have had experiences where I couldn't recall a word (...) or sometimes I use the wrong word (...) which has a significant impact, and makes me feel less confident about using that word.”

FLCA-teacher**Experience a Negative Teaching Style**

Two tokens were counted in this regard. There are also more participants who had unfavourable experiences with teaching styles; that made their FLCA increase. For example, according to Participant 3, not much clarification or supportive feedback from the teachers increased her anxiety. They described how it would be if a teacher just stood there, not saying a word in case the student said something; it really increased pressure and decreased confidence. Participant 6 and 7 stated that their anxiety was maximized by such behaviors of the teacher who was very strict and not so friendly, especially when important tasks like presentations were being conducted.

Interviewee 3: p. 9, line 10 - 12

“Yeah. And the professor is kind of like, strict, I mean, not in a bad way, but more like. If they're not as (...) friendly, I would be like anxious.”

FLCA-peers**Attending in a Big Class**

There are two participants mentioned that attending large classes significantly contributing to FLCA; these are Participants 3 and 7. Participant 3 made the observation that studying in large lecture rooms where one is surrounded by unfamiliar faces heightened her anxiety. Likewise,

Participant 7 mentioned that having big class sizes made her feel judged and observed, which added to the anxiety. Performing in front of a large group becomes pressing, and there is a fear of making mistakes with respect to such exposures.

Interviewee 3: p. 9, line 3 - 5

“And, on the other hand, one thing that decreases my enjoyment in speaking English is that when I’m in big classes (...) with, like, you know, big lectures room.”

4.2.2 Sources of FLE

Category	FLE-self	FLE-teacher	FLE-peers
Source	having an opportunity to speak in a foreign language (3); preparing the lessons in advance (2); having some background knowledge (2)	experiencing a positive teaching style (2)	attending in a supportive classroom environment (2); attending in a small class (2)
In total	7	2	4

Table 5: Three Categories of FLE and the Number of Tokens

The table above Table 5 shows the categorizations of FLE sources. From the table, it clearly has the general categorization in the study groups them into three majors: FLE-self, FLE-teacher, and FLE-peers, with all the categories consisting of specific sources of enjoyment stated by the participants. Factors self-related were most affected, followed by teacher-related and peer-related factors.

The FLE-self category presents the various self-related sources of enjoyment. Students reported that they had the chance to speak in a foreign language (3), to prepare the lessons in advance (2), and to have a bit of background knowledge (2). All in all, 7 tokens of self-related enjoyment sources were reported.

This category, the other was mentioned only when people liked the teacher. More specifically, the enjoyment of a positive teaching style was brought up once in this category, and there were 2 tokens in all.

The FLE-peers category is all about enjoyment from interaction with peers. Participants reported supportive classroom environments and big classes as sources of their enjoyment; thus, there were 4 tokens in this category.

FLE-self

Having an Opportunity to Speak in a Foreign Language

Participant 4 stressed in increasing self-confidence and the pleasure taken from a significant impact on English-speaking practice with native speakers and classmates. She said that vast communication practice allowed her to learn to express her thoughts clearly and, as an outcome of it, to reduce anxiety with time. Along these same lines, Participant 5 opted for much practice in class because, according to them, it was so important and gave the students confidence in what they were doing. Similarly, Participant 7 said that practice and speaking in real situations would decrease anxiety and increase confidence. Engagement with conversational activities may have made the students feel more familiar and comfortable using the language in academic situations, particularly with native speakers."

Interviewee 4: p. 12, line 27 - 29

“...because I have good environment, as I mentioned before, they quite encourage, and I feel comfortable to talk, even though I don't know how to say that. But my friends also help me. Yes, that's it.”

Preparing the Lessons in Advance

For two participants, this was achieved in the way of lesson preparation for Participants 3 and 6, which provides a sense of FLE. Participant 3 noted that their anxiety decreased dramatically through prior preparation for lessons. Reading the material needed for preparation and understanding these provided participation from an informed point of view. Similarly, Participant 6 noted that if well prepared for class, one could take hold of anxiety and hence enjoy doing speaking activities. This participant added that prior preparation through the review of slides and materials from the professor allowed him to feel better and have a sense of self-confidence when participating.

Interviewee 3: p. 8, line 16 - 18

“Once I study in advance. Like I know, I understand the lesson before I come to class. I know what I know what's in my mind. I know what to share. Then then I'll be like, Okay, this is enjoyable.”

Having Some Background Knowledge

Participant 2 stated that having a solid foundation in and a great deal of familiarity with the content increased her confidence and made the experience more enjoyable. In the same vein,

Participant 5 indicated that being an experienced English teacher made her more confident and enjoy using the language in class.

They remarked that, with the advantage of background knowledge about the activities and prior experience in teaching English, they were able to join more comfortably in the class's discussions and other activities, which lessened their anxiety and made them enjoy more.

Interviewee 5: p. 14, line 39 - 41

“So, yeah, I think, like, because background knowledge and background experience will help me like, feel very confident when speaking this in the international class. (...) Okay, so every time.”

FLE-teacher

Experiencing a Positive Teaching Style

A significant component in contributing to the reduction of FLCA and strengthening FLE was found to be a positive teaching style experienced by the participants. Participant 1 declared that he felt better when the atmosphere in the classroom was one of support and understanding—devoid of judgment. Participant 6 added more light on how a positive teaching style influenced learning for them; friendly, approachable, and positively reinforcing teachers helped them be less anxious. The only way these constructive teachers were said to be able to make the learning process fun and not a stressful endeavour is by inspiring feedback and participation without the fear of making a mistake.

Interviewee 6: p. 20, line 6 - 9

“I enjoyed discussing with friends and participating in group activities more than presenting in front of the class. I enjoyed. Em, speaking with professors who are opened and listened to

all students, opinions more than professor with those who (...) Em, expect teaching style of my professor affects my feelings a lot.”

FLE-peers

Attending in a Supportive Classroom Environment

Participant 2 added that their anxiety decreased, and their enjoyment increased in a supportive environment. They felt more at ease and less judged when their peers and teachers were encouraging and understanding, allowing them to be active members in the class. Participant 4 also stated that the ambiance gives the classroom a support factor. They mentioned that supportive friends and teachers, with an encouraging nature to bring in a positive environment, will make them more comfortable to speak up with decent activities.

Interviewee 2: p. 6, line 28 - 30

“Great! I (...) think the environment of classroom really like influences on like speaking anxiety or enjoyment, because like like I mentioned on this like supportive or positive atmosphere in class is really relevant to speaking.”

Attending in a Small Class

Participant 3 highlighted the problem of smaller classes, where one is able to see familiar faces, making an added comfort factor in contributing toward a supportive learning environment. Similarly, Participant 7 pointed out that small group activities and discussions considerably reduced anxiety about the lesson and significantly heightened enjoyment. They were more comfortable and thus in positions of engaging in active participation without that much fear of making mistakes. They felt less judged and more encouraged to speak when in a smaller, more interactive setting.

Interviewee 3: p. 8, line 36 - 38

“Okay, so I'm gonna go with, the increase of enjoyment first. I have noticed, like myself, when I was in a small class with like familiar students, or like and like the learning style, the teaching style of the professors...”

5. Discussion

RQ: 1 What are the general profiles of FLCA and FLE specifically in relation to speaking skills among Thai postgraduate TESOL learners based in the UK?

The first research question examines the general profiles of FLCA and FLE in relation to speaking skills among Thai postgraduate TESOL students based in the UK. The findings indicate that the average score for FLE is 87.70, which is somewhat higher than that for FLCA at 75.57. These results align with previous studies, such as those by (Horwitz et al., 1986; MacIntyre & Gardner, 1994; Gregersen & Horwitz, 2002; Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2014; Dewaele & Dewaele, 2020; Botes et al., 2023; Dewaele et al., 2024). which highlight the significant impact of anxiety and enjoyment in language learning contexts.

FLCA's impact on learners' speaking experiences is significant. Students primarily worry about poor performance, which induces anxiety about peer and teacher perceptions, especially during speaking assignments. Presentation tasks are major anxiety triggers, consistent with the research by Horwitz et al. (1986), Al-Khotaba et al. (2019), and Jiang & Dewaele (2019). Additionally, inadequate preparation and lack of background knowledge exacerbate this anxiety, making students feel more vulnerable and unprepared (Richard, 2020).

Classroom dynamics and teaching styles also significantly influence these experiences. Larger class sizes and new peers contribute to heightened anxiety, with some students reporting that intimidating teaching methods further increase their anxiety levels (Dewaele et al., 2023; Dewaele & Saito, 2024). Conversely, thorough preparation for classes and opportunities to use the language support FLE. Well-prepared students who can apply their language skills in relevant contexts speak with greater enjoyment and confidence. Positive and encouraging teaching methods lower anxiety, increase enjoyment, and foster a supportive learning environment (Dewaele et al., 2022).

Supportive classroom environments, where students can make mistakes without fear of serious consequences, lead to improved learning outcomes. Students feel more comfortable, are more likely to participate actively, and perform better in smaller, more familiar classes (Myhre et al., 2023). The study highlights the importance of self-perception in the dynamics of FLCA and FLE. Positive self-perception correlates with better FLE scores, enhanced confidence, and greater enjoyment of classroom activities, indicating a strong link between linguistic proficiency and self-esteem (Gregersen & Horwitz, 2002).

The study's conclusions have clear implications for instructional approaches. Educators should aim to create classroom conditions that minimize anxiety triggers by establishing a friendly environment, using positive reinforcement, and promoting peer support. Instructional strategies should provide students with ample opportunities to interact with the language realistically and competently, which is crucial for reducing anxiety and increasing enjoyment.

Teachers can modify their teaching strategies to better suit the needs of postgraduate TESOL students from other countries as well as Thai students by knowing how FLCA and FLE affect speaking abilities. This all-encompassing viewpoint emphasises how crucial individual and contextual factors are in determining educational experiences and results.

RQ: 2 What are the relationships between FLCA and FLE with a specific focus on speaking skills among these individuals?

The second research question examines the relationships between FLCA and FLE, focusing specifically on speaking skills among Thai postgraduate TESOL students. The findings reveal an inverse correlation, indicating that students with lower levels of FLCA tend to exhibit higher levels of FLE. This inverse relationship suggests that reducing anxiety can enhance enjoyment, potentially improving overall language learning outcomes.

These insights align with the foundational work of Horwitz et al. (1986) and Dewaele & MacIntyre (2014), who highlighted how anxiety can impede full engagement in language learning by diminishing enjoyment, which is crucial for language acquisition success. Participants reported that situations typically increasing anxiety, such as conducting presentations, speaking in a foreign language, and fear of judgment by peers and instructors, were associated with decreased FLE. This is consistent with findings by Gregersen & Horwitz (2002) and Al-Khotaba et al. (2019), who noted that fear of negative evaluation and high-stakes speaking activities significantly contribute to FLCA.

Similarly, Richards (2020) emphasized that lack of preparation and background knowledge can exacerbate anxiety, making learners feel more exposed and unprepared. Dewaele et al. (2022) and Tsang & Dewaele (2023) support these findings by showing that learners with higher self-

perceived language proficiency tend to experience lower anxiety levels and report greater enjoyment in the learning process.

Conversely, supportive classroom environments characterized by inspiring teaching methods and positive reinforcement significantly enhance FLE. Botes (2017) and Dewaele & Li (2022) demonstrated that positive teacher behaviors and a constructive classroom atmosphere are essential for reducing anxiety and enhancing enjoyment in language learning. Participants noted that having prepared lessons in advance and possessing some background knowledge also increased FLE, as these factors boosted their confidence and made them feel more comfortable during speaking activities. This suggests that increasing learners' confidence in their language abilities can be an effective method in preventing FLCA, aligning with findings by Dewaele & Saito (2019).

The role of self-perception in the dynamics of FLCA and FLE is also significant. Gregersen & Horwitz (2002) found that positive self-perception or higher FLE scores are associated with increased confidence and greater enjoyment of classroom activities. This shows a strong correlation between linguistic proficiency and self-esteem.

Practical implications for language educators include incorporating more supportive and interactive teaching methods, such as peer discussions, role-playing activities, debates, and small-group tasks, to help reduce anxiety and increase enjoyment. Reducing the size of speaking groups or classes may also help mitigate feelings of exposure and judgment, further lowering FLCA and enhancing FLE. This aligns with recommendations by Dewaele et al. (2022) and Thumvichit (2022), who suggest that smaller, familiar classes foster a more supportive learning environment conducive to enjoyment and active participation.

While this study contributes valuable insights, further research is needed across different cultural contexts and various educational settings to explore these dynamics more broadly. Longitudinal studies would also be beneficial to understand how changes in teaching methods and classroom dynamics over time affect FLCA and FLE.

RQ: 3 According to the learners, what are the sources of FLCA and FLE when it comes to speaking skills?

For the third question of my research, which deals with the sources of FLCA and FLE regarding speaking skills, Thai TESOL postgraduate students have identified a few influential factors that affect them. The pressure when doing presentations significantly heightens FLCA because of the public-speaking aspect and the scrutiny from peers and instructors. Apart from the generalized fear of judgment and lack of confidence in their speaking capabilities, the learners are made more anxious by large classes where the intensity of scrutiny is magnified. This inadequacy in preparation for speaking engagements increases anxiety, leaving students feeling unprepared for the demands of speaking tasks (Richards, 2020).

Conversely, the sources of FLE are integrally related both with positive classroom environments and effective teaching styles. Supportive environments where students feel nurtured and supported make FLE much more engaging for students. They elicit a greater readiness to participate actively in class activities and therefore make the learning process enjoyable. Stimulating teachers enhance the enjoyment of learning by creating a positive atmosphere in which students are motivated, which contributes to enhancing their overall experience. Effective communication during class activities also increases satisfaction and enjoyment among students when they can get their ideas across well. Group discussions and

interactive language games are included in the activities, among others, and make the learning environment dynamic and engaging while, hence, amplifying FLE further (Myhre et al., 2023).

All results obtained in this study confirm that also the teaching approach and physical classroom environment contribute to these feelings. In traditional classrooms, FLE increases with direct interactions and engaging teacher behaviors that support a spontaneous, supportive, and interactive atmosphere.

In contrast, distance learning environments can significantly increase students' isolation, thereby reducing FLE and potentially increasing anxiety due to the lack of immediate, face-to-face interaction in a class (Li & Wei, 2022). Properly engaging students by various instructional methods that involve them interactively and lead to personally relevant feedback are important for making students feel valued and less anxious while improving learning.

Rigid methods of teaching or negative teacher behavior, on the other hand, might increase FLCA and create an environment where fear and stress do not allow students to feel engaged and enjoy their studies. Lastly, the personality of students is very important in learning. For instance, perfectionist learners or learners with low self-perceived speaking ability are more prone to suffering from FLCA (Kitano, 2001; Gregersen & Horwitz, 2002). On the other hand, introverted personalities with a higher emotional intelligence manifest in higher FLE and are therefore better performers in most of the learning outcomes (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2019; Li, 2020). This understanding makes it very important for educators to be able to design their strategies in instruction in such a way that they would reduce anxiety and increase enjoyment.

The educational outcome and the emotional well-being of students can be improved if educators design the learning environment such that the FLCA triggers reduce and the factors contributing to the development of FLE are increased, making this learning a more effective and enjoyable experience.

6. Limitations

The study has certainly opened a window to FLCA and FLE within the academic setting of Thai TESOL postgraduate students in the United Kingdom, but there are still limitations. First and foremost, it could only use 14 participants, which usually limits the generalizability of research findings across populations. Moreover, using only two male participants in the study, all qualitative interviews were among female participants; this potentially leads to gender bias in findings that are not likely to represent accurately the experiences of male students.

The use of a method of data collection that highly depends on self-reported measures via questionnaires and interviews may also pose problems when it comes to data bias. Although the researcher tried to clarify the items, participants might misremember or even over-report more positively on their experiences, especially when talking about sensitive issues such as anxiety and enjoyment in foreign language classrooms. Caution might have needed to be taken for the interpretation of the findings because this reliance on self-report might not have totally captured the complexity of the emotional experience.

The other limitation is that it is cross-sectional; therefore, it captures only a snapshot in time, and no analysis was done on how FLCA and FLE develop across time. This undermines the opportunity to find the cause and determine the lasting influence of such emotions on language

learning. Longitudinal research would thus be better for investigating these processes in more detail.

The specific focus on Thai TESOL postgraduate students in the UK also places cultural and contextual constraints on the study findings and potentially, therefore, compromises their general applicability to Thai students in different contexts or to international students from diverse cultures. Cultural influences are key factors in shaping emotional experiences that cannot be perfectly captured in the findings from this study.

7. Implications

These findings bear several possible implications that can be enlightening for language educators, program developers, and policy makers, especially in the context of Thai TESOL postgraduate students in the UK. Research shows that a supportive teaching environment can decrease FLCA while increasing FLE in learning activities. As suggested by Dewaele & MacIntyre (2014) and further discussed in the literature, educators are urged to implement participative teaching styles and provide constructive feedback, fostering a positive learning environment that benefits students in group settings while also lessening fear of negative evaluation (Botes et al., 2023). This approach allows educators to better personalize instruction to mitigate triggers of anxiety and maximize sources of enjoyment for their students.

The literature review reveals that teacher behavior plays a major role in both FLCA and FLE, advocating for positive nurturing pedagogies. For example, learning contexts that incorporate humour, praise, and communicative practices can boost student engagement and willingness to learn (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2019). Smaller class sizes and more familiar class dynamics are shown to decrease anxiety and enhance learning outcomes (Myhre et al., 2023).

Moreover, the study addresses the importance of cultural aspects in language education. Given that Thai TESOL postgraduate students are navigating a new cultural and educational system, it is necessary for educators to integrate culturally appropriate teaching techniques (Jiang & Dewaele, 2019; Chinpakdee, 2015). Understanding the cultural backgrounds of students can help educators create curricula and instructional strategies that align with the students' emotional and academic needs.

The implications extend beyond individual classroom practices to program development and educational policy. Institutions should provide training programs for educators to enhance their awareness of FLCA and FLE and equip them with strategies to address these emotions in the classroom (Horwitz, 2017). Educational policies should focus on creating conducive conditions for learning, supporting emotional well-being, and facilitating linguistic and cultural adaptation, particularly for international students (Bhattachaiyakorn & Phettakua, 2023).

In conclusion, addressing individual emotional needs ensures that students remain motivated and engaged, ultimately leading to success in language learning. Educators can influence not only academic outcomes but also long-term well-being by fostering a supportive, low anxiety learning environment (Gregersen & Horwitz, 2002; Dewaele & Saito, 2024). These implications offer valuable insights for optimizing language learning experiences and outcomes for diverse student populations.

8. Conclusion

The study has delineated this intricate relationship between FLCA and FLE among Thai TESOL postgraduate students working towards degrees in the UK. It identifies major factors contributing to anxiety and enjoyable speaking, whilst also providing comprehensive insights into how it relates to second language speaking quality and overall academic performance, as echoed by Horwitz et al. (1986).

This also lends credence to the view of Dewaele et al. (2014, 2022, 2023) who contended that experienced enjoyment enhances motivation and engagement. It implies that fostering a supportive teaching practice might reduce FLCA and increase FLE. Creating a classroom that is positive reinforcement-based, has smaller class sizes, and incorporates culturally relevant teaching methods fosters an environment where language learning can grow.

The present study contributes to the existing literature as it shines a light on specific emotional dimensions from an international academic setting among Thai postgraduate students, highlighting the cultural importance in language education. It is at the same time consistent with Chinpakdee (2015) and Bhattarachaiyakorn & Phettakua (2023), who portray challenges faced by learners, particularly Thai students overseas.

Future research could more systematically investigate these dynamics over time and across cultures and educational settings with larger samples. This will contribute to a better understanding of the evolution and lasting effects that FLCA or FLE can have on language achievement over time. This illustration can enable educators and policymakers to recognize the complexity of emotions to better support students in achieving self-actualization, which goes beyond typical academic outcomes.

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10. Appendices

Appendix 1: Coding Scheme of Interviews

Categories	Codes	Definitions	Examples
Sources of Anxiety	SIFL	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they speak in foreign language in classroom settings.	<p>“When I’m anxious, I tend to speak less and hesitate more which can hinder my participation.”</p> <p>“In the beginning of my studies I felt quite nervous and shy when I had to speak English in class.”</p>
	BJ	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they might be being judged in classroom settings by others.	<p>“But nervousness was due to making mistake or being judged by peers.”</p> <p>“I feel like I was worried about making mistake and being judged by my classmates, all my teachers.”</p>
	MM	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they might make mistakes in classroom settings by others.	<p>“The main source of anxiety for me are fear of making mistake.”</p> <p>“So (...) I’m afraid to making mistake, being judged by peer or teacher, especially when it comes to the high stake speaking tasks.”</p>
	LOP	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they might lack of preparation in classroom settings.	<p>“The situation that got me anxious would be when I show up in classroom, and I didn't prepare the lesson.”</p>

Categories	Codes	Definitions	Examples
	PT	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they conducted a presentation in classroom settings.	<p>“My classmates are also like watching me presenting. So it's like it's really, really nervous.”</p> <p>“Sometimes the complexity of the language test high-stake situation like exam or presentation also adds to my anxiety, too.”</p>
	BC	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they attend in a big class.	“And, on the other hand, one thing that decreases my enjoyment in speaking English is that when I'm in big classes (...) with, like, you know, big lectures room.”
	NTS	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they experience a negative teaching style.	“When the professors seem to be like waiting, waiting for my answers like, keep waiting. They're not like giving more words or more instructions, or they do not like elaborate. They do not explain. They just wait for my answer, like silently, like dead airing, something like that. And I'd be like, okay, I got even like more anxious.”

Categories	Codes	Definitions	Examples
	LBK	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they lack of some background knowledge.	“I have had experience where I felt quite anxious when I had to express my opinion on the topics that I'm not very familiar with”
Sources of Enjoyment	DCE	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they attend in a decent classroom environment.	“The factors that contribute to my enjoyment include engaging and relevant topics, supportive peers and instructors, relaxing classroom environment (...) and (...) activity that are both challenging and achievable.”
	SC	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they attend in a small class.	<p>“I think that one really like help me to reduce my anxiety because I don't have to speak in a whole class, but to small group of people.”</p> <p>“We have been in the same classes before last term. So, when I'm in class with only these students in my program, I feel like really like enjoyed.”</p>

Categories	Codes	Definitions	Examples
	PTS	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they experience a positive teaching style.	<p>“The factors that contribute to my enjoyment include engaging and relevant topics, supportive peers and instructors, relaxing classroom environment.</p> <p>“the environment was supportive and everyone just encouraged me to speak, and in a positive way.”</p> <p>“Instructors who used interactive and communicative teaching method (...) provide a constructive feedback and encourage participation enhance my enjoyment.”</p>
	PP	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they prepare the lessons in advance.	<p>“I prepare in advance, like reading loops, reading professor slides. (...) so I think it can reduce my anxiety.”</p> <p>“Okay, it's enjoyable. Once I study in advance.”</p>

Categories	Codes	Definitions	Examples
	OSFL	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they have an opportunity to speak in a foreign language.	<p>“But in terms of enjoyment I also found that it's a great opportunity to express myself and practice speaking to, because”</p> <p>“So I always enjoy to speak English and share my opinion in English.”</p>
	HBK	This code can be used when interviewees mentions that they have some background knowledge.	<p>“So, yeah, I think, like, because background knowledge and background experience will help me feel very confident when speaking this in the international class”</p> <p>“This is like the background, and the progress, life experience, is really important for me.”</p>

Appendix 2: Interview Transcriptions

Transcription key:

- 1.Pause less than 3 seconds: (...)
- 2.Pause more than 3 seconds: (.....)
- 3.Laugh: (LF)
- 4.Fillers: Em/Uh

1 Interviewee 7

2 **Time: Jun 12, 2024 13:15 – 13:30**

3 Researcher: Can you describe your initial feelings about speaking in a foreign
4 language, in classroom settings?

5

6 Interviewee: Okay, like. (...) just get back. For like a few months ago, initially, when I
7 just started speaking in the classroom in the UK, I feel quite nervous and self
8 conscious when I speak in a foreign language in a classroom setting. I feel like I was
9 worried about making mistake and being judged by my classmates, all my teachers.
10 (...) and I feel like this fear often made me feel hesitate to participate in the speaking
11 activities in the classroom.

12

13 Researcher: How do you perceive you speaking skills in a foreign language
14 compared to your classmates?

15

16 Interviewee: I think my speaking skills as (...) somewhat average is in the moderate
17 level compared to my classmates, because, like some of my classmates are the
18 native speakers that (...) that's mean. They are more fluent and more confident when
19 they are speaking English. Why, some people just struggle as me because they are
20 nonnative speaker. I feel like this. Variation often depends on each individual
21 background or prior exposure to the language. So for me, I feel like I am a moderate,
22 not that super good, but not bad.

23

24 Researcher: In what ways do you feel your background or prior experiences
25 influence your feelings of anxiety or enjoyment when speaking in a foreign language?

26

27 Interviewee: I feel like my background or my prior experience in using language is
28 really important to the anxiety and enjoyment. When I use language because I grew
29 up in the country, that is non English speaking country with a limited opportunity to
30 practice speaking English outside a classroom. So I feel like when I use English in
31 real life. This makes me (...) very, very anxious, and cause a lot of anxiety in my life,
32 but I have an experience as a teacher's for 7 years. I try to speak English with my
33 native speaker, friends or co-worker, and use English in class. I feel like this activity,
34 help me to enjoy the process, and enjoy speaking, and build my confidence over and
35 over time.

36

37 Researcher: Can you share any specific experiences where you felt particularly
38 anxious or enjoyed while speaking in a foreign language during class?

39

40

41 Interviewee: Sure. One specific experience that made me very anxious (...) is during
42 my presentation in the 1st semester. (...) Yeah, I feel like a lot of pressure to perform
43 well, and it made me like very nervous. But I feel like my group, my friends in a
44 group, does help me a lot to get over this one. And I feel like I enjoy participating in
45 group discussion more because, like the environment was supportive and everyone
46 just encouraged me to speak, and in a positive way.

47

48 Researcher: How do these experiences relate to your performance or participation in
49 speaking activities?

50

51 Interviewee: Okay, my anxiety during the presentation just makes me decrease my
52 performance. I guess I spoke less clearly, and I just forgot some important points that
53 I want to convey to my classmate. (...) But as I say that the supportive group
54 discussion just was my confident, because they just allow me to participate more and
55 like, just let me express my idea more freely, because, you know, like in the
56 presentation, you have to focus on the content. And you have to like. (...) speak
57 everything that is specific for the presentation. But for the group (...) discussion, you
58 can speak something freely, and you don't have to worry about the content.

59

60 Researcher: Have you noticed any patterns or conditions under which your
61 enjoyment increases or your anxiety decreases during speaking tasks?

62

63 Interviewee: Sure I've noticed that my enjoyment increases, and anxiety decreases
64 when I am in the supportive environment, like my friends, just help me encourage me
65 or my teachers just try to understand me, even though I just speak something wrong
66 or ungrammatically, and the thing that I feel like the most supportive thing. It's just
67 like small group activity and small group discussion (...) that I feel less judged and
68 everyone just helps me try to understand me that reduces my anxiety.

69

70 Researcher: What factors do you think contribute most to your feelings of enjoyment
71 when you are required to speak in a foreign language in class?

72

73 Interviewee: Okay. The 1st one is the vibe in the classroom, especially from my
74 peers and my teachers. If you like the supportive classroom environment, just helps
75 me a lot, and then a constructive feedback from my instructor that then try not to
76 judge, but try to help me try to correct me in the nice way, if I just speak something
77 wrong. (...) and they just give me the chance to engage in the class, even though I
78 feel like okay, my English is not that good. But they just give me the opportunity to
79 speak in like in the public way or in the discussion. (...) and I feel like the one that
80 encourages me the most is interactive activities that make me learn process with the
81 fun and like non intimidating vibe, yeah.

82 Researcher: Conversely, What are the main sources of anxiety for you when it
83 comes to speaking tasks?

84

85 Interviewee: Okay. The main thing of anxiety for me are the fear of making mistakes.
86 We just study and born in the country that everyone just expects us to speak English
87 perfectly, but, in fact, if we are a nonnative, we cannot do that perfectly, even though,
88 like the native speaker, cannot speak English perfectly right. So (...) I'm afraid to
89 making mistake, being judged by peer or teacher, especially when it comes to the
90 high stake speaking tasks. (...) I really really anxious about this one like presentation
91 when we have a pressure to perform well in front of a lot of people (...).

92

93 Researcher: How do you manage these feelings of enjoyment and anxiety to
94 improve your speaking skills?

95

96 Interviewee: The 1st thing, it is a skill. So, when I want to manage this feeling, I just
97 manage by practicing regularly. I just like. Repeat that again and again by myself in
98 front of the mirror to make sure that okay, when I speak in the real situation, I barely
99 make mistake, and then maybe I just seek some feedback from my peer or from my
100 coworker, that (...) the way that I speak upon way is good enough And then I just forgot on
101 my improvement. (...) I don't think like, okay, we can like or understandable.
102 improve from the low to the high in a few days, but it is like improvement gradually,
103 and I don't seek for the perfection anymore right now. I just seek for like, okay, if the
104 other people just understand me. That's okay. That reaches the goal of like speaking
105 or conversation.

106

107 Researcher: How that's the classroom environment and teaching style affect your
108 feelings of anxiety or enjoyment during speaking activities? Can you give examples
109 of specific environmental or instructional factors that either alleviate your anxieties or
110 enhance your enjoyment.

111

112 Interviewee: Okay, I think the classroom environment and teaching style of the
113 teacher just affect my feelings. For example, a teacher who give me a positive
114 reinforcement and create a safe space for making mistake is very, very important to
115 decrease my anxiety, and (...) I feel like the high-pressure environment tends to
116 increase my anxiety more when I be in the class. So I feel like activities, like a casual
117 debate, or the small group discussion, or everything that makes me feel relaxed. I feel
118 like this setting can enhance my enjoyment and encourage me to participate more in in
119 speaking activities.

120

Appendix 3: Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale

Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale

Horwitz, E. K., Horwitz, M. B., & Cope, J. (1986). Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety. *The Modern Language Journal*, 70(2), 125-132.

No.	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I never feel quite sure of myself when I am speaking in my foreign language class.					
2	I don't worry about making mistakes in language class.					
3	I tremble when I know that I'm going to be called on in language class.					
4	It frightens me when I don't understand what the teacher is saying in the foreign language.					
5	It wouldn't bother me at all to take more foreign language classes.					
6	During language class, I find myself thinking about things that have nothing to do with the course.					
7	I keep thinking that the other students are better at languages than I am.					
8	I am usually at ease during tests in my language class.					
9	I start to panic when I have to speak without preparation in language class.					
10	I worry about the consequences of failing my foreign language class.					
11	I don't understand why some people get so upset over foreign language classes.					
12	In language class, I can get so nervous I forget things I know.					
13	It embarrasses me to volunteer answers in my language class.					
14	I would not be nervous speaking the foreign language with native speakers.					
15	I get upset when I don't understand what the teacher is correcting.					

No.	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
16	Even if I am well prepared for language class, I feel anxious about it.					
17	I often feel like not going to my language class.					
18	I feel confident when I speak in foreign language class.					
19	I am afraid that my language teacher is ready to correct every mistake I make.					
20	I can feel my heart pounding when I'm going to be called on in language class.					
21	The more I study for a language test, the more confused I get.					
22	I don't feel pressure to prepare very well for language class.					
23	I always feel that the other students speak the foreign language better than I do.					
24	I feel very self-conscious about speaking the foreign language in front of other students.					
25	Language class moves so quickly I worry about getting left behind.					
26	I feel more tense and nervous in my language class than in my other classes.					
27	I get nervous and confused when I am speaking in my language class.					
28	When I'm on my way to language class, I feel very sure and relaxed.					
29	I get nervous when I don't understand every word the language teacher says.					
30	I feel overwhelmed by the number of rules you have to learn to speak a foreign language.					
31	I am afraid that the other students will laugh.					

Appendix 4: Foreign Language Enjoyment Scale

Foreign Language Enjoyment Scale

Botes, E., Dewaele, J., & Greiff, S. (2021). The development and validation of the short form of the foreign language enjoyment scale. *The Modern Language Journal*, 105(4), 858-876.

No.	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I can be creative.					
2	I can laugh off embarrassing mistakes in the FL.					
3	I don't get bored.					
4	I enjoy it.					
5	I feel as though I'm a different person during the FL class.					
6	I learned to express myself better in the FL.					
7	I'm a worthy member of the FL class.					
8	I've learned interesting things.					
9	In class, I feel proud of my accomplishments.					
10	It's a positive environment.					
11	It's cool to know a foreign language.					
12	It's fun.					
13	Making errors is part of the learning process.					
14	The peers are nice.					
15	The teacher is encouraging.					
16	The teacher is friendly.					
17	The teacher is supportive.					
18	There is a good atmosphere.					
19	We form a tight group.					
20	We have common "legends", such as running jokes.					
21	We laugh a lot.					

Appendix 5: Interview Questions

The interview questions are based on this paper below.

Dörnyei, Z. (2005). *The Psychology of the Language Learner: Individual Differences in Second Language Acquisition*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.

Ice-breaking Questions

1. Can you tell me about yourself?
2. Why did you choose to study TESOL in the UK

General Profiles of FLCA and FLE

1. Can you describe your initial feelings about speaking in a foreign language in classroom settings?
2. How do you perceive your speaking skills in a foreign language compared to your classmates?
3. In what ways do you feel your background or prior experiences influence your feelings of anxiety or enjoyment when speaking in a foreign language?

Relationships between FLE and FLCA in Speaking Skills

4. Can you share any specific experiences where you felt particularly anxious or enjoyed while speaking in a foreign language during class?
5. How do these experiences relate to your performance or participation in speaking activities?
6. Have you noticed any patterns or conditions under which your enjoyment increases, or your anxiety decreases during speaking tasks?

Sources of FLE and FLCA in Speaking Skills

7. What factors do you think contribute most to your feelings of enjoyment when you are required to speak in a foreign language in class?
8. Conversely, what are the main sources of anxiety for you when it comes to speaking tasks?
9. How do you manage these feelings of enjoyment and anxiety to improve your speaking skills?
10. How does the classroom environment and teaching style affect your feelings of anxiety or enjoyment during speaking activities? Can you give examples of specific environmental or instructional factors that either alleviate your anxiety or enhance your enjoyment?

Appendix 6: Ethics Application Form

IOE – FACULTY OF EDUCATION AND SOCIETY

Ethics Application Form: Student Research

Anyone conducting research under the auspices of the Institute (staff, students or visitors) where the research involves human participants or the use of data collected from human participants, is required to gain ethical approval before starting. This includes preliminary and pilot studies. Please answer all relevant questions in terms that can be understood by a lay person and note that your form may be returned if incomplete.

For further support and guidance please see accompanying guidelines and the Ethics Review Procedures for Student Research or contact your supervisor.

Before completing this form you will need to discuss your proposal fully with your supervisor(s).

Please attach all supporting documents and letters.

For all Psychology students, this form should be completed with reference to the British Psychological Society (BPS) Code of Human Research Ethics and Code of Ethics and Conduct.

Section 1: Project Details

- a) Project title: A study examining the foreign language classroom anxiety and enjoyment in relation to speaking skills of Thai postgraduates studying in the TESOL program in the United Kingdom
- b) Student name: Seksan Thongthai (dtnvst8@ucl.ac.uk)
- c) Supervisor/Personal Tutor: Dr. Celia-Vasiliki Antoniou (celia.antoniou@ucl.ac.uk)
- d) Department: School of Culture, Communication and Media, Institute of Education
- e) Course category (tick one):
 - PhD/MPhil
 - EdD
 - MRes
 - DEdPsy

- MTeach
- MA/MSc
- ITE
- Diploma (state which) Enter text
- Other (state which) Enter text
- f) Course/module title: [Dissertation Applied Linguistics and TESOL](#)
- g) If applicable, state who the funder is and if funding has been confirmed:
Enter text
- h) Intended research start date: [16 May, 2024](#)
- i) Intended research end date: [28 August, 2024](#)
- j) Country fieldwork will be conducted in: [the UK](#)

If research to be conducted abroad please check the [Foreign and Commonwealth Office \(FCO\)](#) and submit a completed travel risk assessment form (see guidelines). If the FCO advice is against travel this will be required before ethical approval can be granted: [UCL travel advice webpage](#)

- k) Has this project been considered by another (external) Research Ethics Committee?

Yes

External Committee Name: Enter text

Date of Approval: Enter text

No **go to Section 2**

If yes:

- Submit a copy of the approval letter with this application.
- Proceed to Section 10 Attachments.

Note: Ensure that you check the guidelines carefully as research with some participants will require ethical approval from a different ethics committee such as the [National Research Ethics Service](#) (NRES) or [Social Care Research Ethics Committee](#) (SCREC). In addition, if your research is based in another institution then you may be required to apply to their research ethics committee.

Section 2 - Research methods summary (tick all that apply)

- Interviews
- Focus Groups
- Questionnaires
- Action Research
- Observation
- Literature Review
- Controlled trial/other intervention study

- Use of personal records
- Systematic review – **if only method used go to Section 5**
- Secondary data analysis – **if secondary analysis used go to Section 6**
- Advisory/consultation/collaborative groups
- Other, give details:

Please provide an overview of the project, focusing on your methodology. This should include some or all of the following: purpose of the research, aims, main research questions, research design, participants, sampling, data collection (including justifications for methods chosen and description of topics/questions to be asked), reporting and dissemination. Please focus on your methodology; the theory, policy, or literary background of your work can be provided in an attached document (i.e. a full research proposal or case for support document). *Minimum 150 words required.*

My proposed study aims to explore the relationship between foreign language classroom anxiety and enjoyment in relation to speaking skills among Thai students in a TESOL program in the UK. By identifying problems and factors contributing to enjoyment, the study seeks to inform best practices in ESL contexts, benefiting universities and policymakers in designing effective international curriculums.

1. What are the general profiles of FLCA and FLE specifically in relation to speaking skills among Thai postgraduate TESOL learners based in the UK?
2. What are the relationships between FLE and FLCA with a specific focus on speaking skills among these individuals?
3. According to the learners, what are the sources of FLE and FLCA when it comes to speaking skills?

The proposed study will utilize an integrated mixed-method approach to collect and analyse both qualitative and quantitative data concerning the emotional experiences of Thai TESOL students in the UK. Two instruments will be employed during the quantitative phase: the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), adapted from Horwitz et al. (1986), and the Foreign Language Enjoyment (FLE) Scale, developed by Dewaele and MacIntyre in 2014. Both scales use a 5-point Likert scale to gauge participant responses. Additionally, semi-structured interviews will be conducted to delve deeper into the students' motivations, coping mechanisms, and contextual influences on their emotional experiences, drawing on methods suggested by Dörnyei (2005).

For data collection, participants will be recruited through snowball sampling, and an online questionnaire will be administered via Google Form. Responses will be analysed using SPSS to identify notable trends and insights, with select participants being invited for further online interviews based on their questionnaire scores. All interview contents will be online via Google Meet which will be audio-recorded and analysed using content analysis techniques. Ethical considerations are paramount; participants will be fully informed about the study's purpose, their rights, including

the right to withdraw, and measures will be taken to ensure their anonymity and ethical treatment throughout the research process.

Section 3 – research Participants (tick all that apply)

- a) Will your research involve human participants?
 Yes
 No (if 'No', go to Section 4)
- b) Who are the participants for this project (i.e. what sorts of people will be involved)? Tick all that apply
- Early years/pre-school
 - Ages 5-11
 - Ages 12-16
 - Young people aged 17-18
 - Adults please specify below
 - Unknown – specify below
 - No participants

The participants are Thai postgraduates studying in the TESOL program in the United Kingdom.

Note: Ensure that you check the guidelines carefully as research with some participants will require ethical approval from a different ethics committee such as the [National Research Ethics Service](#) (NRES) or [Social Care Research Ethics Committee](#) (SCREC).

- c) If participants are under the responsibility of others (such as parents, teachers or medical staff) how do you intend to obtain permission to approach the participants to take part in the study? (*Please attach approach letters or details of permission procedures - see Section 9*)

Participants are adults and they will sign the consent form before taking part in the study.

- d) How will participants be recruited (identified and approached)?

Snowball sampling via Facebook groups and Line application will be used to collect the contact of participants. I will send participant information sheets and consent forms via emails to my potential participants studying in the UK.

- e) Describe the process you will use to inform participants about what you are doing

Once responses are received from the volunteers who are willing to take part in the study, they will be sent a detailed email outlining the study, including information sheets and consent forms. They will be requested to carefully review the attached participant information sheet and consent form included with email.

- f) How will you obtain the consent of participants? Will this be written? How will it be made clear to participants that they may withdraw consent to participate at any time?

Every participant will receive a copy of consent form via email, which they must sign. After that, I will receive the signed paper back, and the participant keep a copy of consent form for themselves. The consent form makes it very clear that participants may withdraw from the study at any time by emailing me personally, and this will also be covered in detail during the study briefing.

- g) **Studies involving questionnaires:** will participants be given the option of omitting questions they do not wish to answer?

Yes

No*

***If no**, please explain why below, and ensure that you cover any ethical issues arising from this in Section 8

Enter text

- h) **Studies involving observation:** please confirm whether participants will be asked for their informed consent to be observed

Yes

No*

***If no**, read the guidelines (Ethical Issues section) and explain why below and ensure that you cover any ethical issues arising from this in section 8

Enter text

- i) Might participants experience anxiety, discomfort, or embarrassment as a result of your study?

Yes*

No*

***If yes**, what steps will you take to explain and minimise this?

Due to the possibility of performing poorly, participants may feel anxious and embarrassed during their interviews. They can stop participating in

the study at any time by emailing me personally, and I will assure them that neither their performance nor their grades will be evaluated. Some questions about learning anxiety might be possibly embarrassing to be asked, so I will make sure that the questions are not too straightforward and sensitive or that they can choose to skip the questions.

***If no**, explain how you can be sure that no discomfort or embarrassment will arise?

Enter text

- j) Will your project involve deliberately misleading participants (deception) in any way?

Yes*

No

If yes, please provide further details below and ensure that you cover any ethical issues arising from this in Section 8

Enter text

- k) Will you debrief participants at the end of their participation (i.e. give them a brief explanation of the study)?

Yes

No*

***If no**, please explain why below and ensure that you cover any ethical issues arising from this in section 8

Enter text

- l) Will participants be given information about the findings of your study? (This could be a brief summary of your findings in general; it is not the same as an individual debriefing)

Yes

No*

If no, why not?

Enter text

Section 4 - Security-sensitive material (only complete if applicable)

Security sensitive research includes: commissioned by the military; commissioned under an EU security call; involves the acquisition of security clearances; concerns terrorist or extreme groups.

- a. Will your project consider or encounter security-sensitive material?
Yes* No
- b. Will you be visiting websites associated with extreme or terrorist organisations?
Yes* No
- c. Will you be storing or transmitting any materials that could be interpreted as promoting or endorsing terrorist acts?
Yes* No

* Give further details in **Section 8 Ethical Issues**

Section 5 – Systematic reviews of research (only complete if applicable)

- a. Will you be collecting any new data from participants?
Yes* No
- b. Will you be analysing any secondary data?
Yes* No

* Give further details in **Section 8 Ethical Issues**

*If your methods do not involve engagement with participants (e.g. systematic review, literature review) **and** if you have answered **No** to both questions, please go to **Section 10 Attachments**.*

Section 6 - Secondary data analysis (only complete if applicable)

- a. Name of dataset/s:
- b. Owner of dataset/s:
- c. Are the data in the public domain?
Yes No

If no, do you have the owner's permission/license?

Yes No*

- d. Are the data special category personal data (i.e. personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation)?
Yes* No
- e. Will you be conducting analysis within the remit it was originally collected for?
Yes No*

- f. **If no**, was consent gained from participants for subsequent/future analysis?
Yes No*
- g. **If no**, was data collected prior to ethics approval process?
Yes No*

* Give further details in **Section 8 Ethical Issues**

*If secondary analysis is only method used **and** no answers with asterisks are ticked, go to **Section 9 Attachments**.*

Section 7 – Data storage and security

- a) Confirm that all personal data will be stored and processed in compliance with the General Data Protection Registration (GDPR). (See the [Guidelines](#) and the Institute's Data Protection & Records Management Policy for more detail.)
Yes
- b) Will personal data be processed or be sent outside of the European Economic Area (EEA)?
Yes*
No

***If yes**, please confirm that there are adequate levels of protections in compliance with the DPA 2018 and state what these arrangements are below

- c) Who will have access to the data and personal information, including advisory/consultation groups, and during transcription?
- l) The researcher Seksan Thongthai (dtnvst8@ucl.ac.uk) the supervisor/Personal Tutor Dr. Celia-Vasiliki Antoniou (celia.antoniou@ucl.ac.uk) will have access to the data and personal information only.

During the research

- d) Where will the data be stored?

The researcher's personal, password-protected laptop and phone will still hold all of the digitalized data. An encrypted cloud backup of the data will also be included, in case these devices malfunction or lose data. The test findings in hard copy will all be stored in a locked, closed cabinet.

- e) Will mobile devices such as USB storage and laptops be used?

Yes

No

***If yes**, state what mobile devices will be used

In a password-protected laptop and a password-protected phone.

After the research

f) Where will the data be stored?

The researcher's personal, password-protected laptop and phone will still hold all of the digitalized data. An encrypted cloud backup of the data will also be included, in case these devices malfunction or lose data. The test findings in hard copy will all be stored in a locked, closed cabinet.

g) How long will the data and records be kept for, and in what format?

At least one year according to UCL guidelines

h) Will the data be archived for use by other researchers?

Yes

No

***If yes**, please provide details

Enter text

Section 8 – Ethical Issues

Are there particular features of the proposed work which may raise ethical concerns or add to the complexity of ethical decision making? If so, please outline how you will deal with these below.

It is important that you demonstrate your awareness of potential risks or harm that may arise as a result of your research. You should then demonstrate that you have considered ways to minimise the likelihood and impact of each potential harm that you have identified. Please be as specific as possible in describing the ethical issues you will have to address. Please consider / address ALL issues that may apply from the below.

Ethical concerns may include, but not be limited to, the following areas:

- Methods
- Sampling
- Recruitment
- Gatekeepers
- Informed consent
- Potentially vulnerable participants
- Safeguarding/child protection

- Sensitive topics
- International research
- Risks to participants and/or researchers
- Confidentiality/Anonymity
- Disclosures/limits to confidentiality
- Data storage and security both during and after the research (including transfer, sharing, encryption, protection)
- Reporting
- Dissemination and use of findings

Recruitment

I will respect volunteers' decisions to decline participation at any time, even if they previously agreed to join the study. Before their involvement, I will clearly communicate essential details about the project, including its objectives, their expected contributions, the required time commitment, and the confidentiality measures in place. Participants will be informed that their involvement is entirely voluntary and they can withdraw at any stage without any obligation to justify their decision. To ensure anonymity and protect privacy, questionnaires will be administered without collecting identifying information, and interviews will use pseudonyms instead of real names. The study will involve 14 participants for the questionnaires and 5 to 7 participants for the interviews, ensuring a secure and respectful environment for honest participation.

Sensitive topics

Sensitive topics could make embarrassment to the participants while conducting an interview because I research on language learning anxiety. However, I will minimise it using a variety of interview questions e.g. ice-breaking questions, main questions, follow-up questions, and wrap-up questions so as to gain as much as valid information. Additionally, the participants will be informed that they can withdraw at any point by emailing me. Also, they can skip a question if it makes them feel uncomfortable during the interview.

Data storage and security both during and after the research (including transfer, sharing, encryption, protection)

The researcher's personal, password-protected laptop and phone will still hold all of the digitalized data. An encrypted cloud backup of the data will also be included, in case these devices malfunction or lose data. The test findings in hard copy will all be stored in a locked, closed cabinet. I will make sure that nobody can access to the data.

Section 9 – Further information

Outline any other information you feel is relevant to this submission, using a separate sheet or attachments if necessary

Enter text

Section 10 – Face to Face data collection (only complete if you will be collecting face to face data outside of the UK)

Provide details of your back-up plan for online data collection methods or secondary data analysis, which will be put into action should you need to cease F2F data collection (max 150 words).

Please note that should you need to change your data collection methods due to a change in Covid19 regulations in the country context of your research (for example, if lockdown is re-introduced) you will need to submit to your supervisor:

- a) a revised information sheet
- b) consent form
- c) details of any additional/different risks linked to online data collection.

In cases where back-up plans have to be implemented, students must not proceed with online data collection until they have received written approval (via email) from their tutor/supervisor.

Enter text

Section 11 – Attachments

Please attach the following items to this form, or explain if not attached:

- a) Information sheets and other materials to be used to inform potential participants about the research, including approach letters
Yes No N/A
- b) Consent form
Yes No N/A
- c) The proposal for the project
Yes No N/A
- d) Approval Letter from external Research Ethics Committee
Yes No N/A
- e) Full risk assessment
Yes No N/A

Section 12 – Declaration

I have read, understood, and will abide by the following set of guidelines:

Yes No

Please select guidelines this project will be abiding by:

BPS

BERA

BSA

Other (please state)

I have discussed the ethics issues relation to my research with my supervisor

Yes No

I have attended the appropriate ethics training provided by my course

Yes No

I confirm that to the best of my knowledge:

The above information is correct and this is a full description of the ethics issues that may arise in the course of this project

Name: [Seksan Thongthai](#)

Date: [7 May 2024](#)

Once complete, please submit your complete ethics forms to your supervisor

Notes & References

Useful links & information

Professional code of ethics

You should read and understand relevant ethics guidelines, for example:

[British Psychological Society](#) (2018) *Code of Ethics and Conduct*

or

[British Educational Research Association](#) (2018) *Ethical Guidelines*

or

[British Sociological Association](#) (2017) *Statement of Ethical Practice*

Please see the respective websites for these or later versions; direct links to the latest versions are available on the [Institute of Education Research Ethics webpage](#)

Disclosure and Barring Service checks

If you are planning to carry out research in regulated Education environments such as Schools, or if your research will bring you into contact with children and young people (under the age of 18), you will need to have a Disclosure and Barring Service (DBS) CHECK, before you start. The DBS was previously known as the Criminal Records Bureau (CRB)). If you do not already hold a current DBS check, and have not registered with the DBS update service, you will need to obtain one through UCL.

Ensure that you apply for the DBS check in plenty of time as will take around 4 weeks, though can take longer depending on the circumstances.

Further references

Robson, Colin (2011). *Real world research: a resource for social scientists and practitioner researchers* (3rd edition). Oxford: Blackwell.

This text has a helpful section on ethical considerations.

Alderson, P. and Morrow, V. (2011) *The Ethics of Research with Children and Young People: A Practical Handbook*. London: Sage.

This text has useful suggestions if you are conducting research with children and young people.

Wiles, R. (2013) *What are Qualitative Research Ethics?* Bloomsbury.

A useful and short text covering areas including informed consent, approaches to research ethics including examples of ethical dilemmas.

Departmental use

If a project raises particularly challenging ethics issues, or a more detailed review would be appropriate, the supervisor must refer the application to the Research Development Administrator via email so that it can be submitted to the IOE Research Ethics Committee for consideration. A departmental research ethics coordinator or representative can advise you, either to support your review process, or help decide whether an application should be referred to the REC. If unsure please refer to the guidelines explaining when to refer the ethics application to the IOE Research Ethics Committee, posted on the committee's website.

Student name: **Seksan Thongthai**

Course: **Dissertation Applied Linguistics and TESOL**

Project Title: **A study examining the foreign language classroom anxiety and enjoyment in relation to speaking skills of Thai postgraduates studying in the TESOL program in the United Kingdom**

Reviewer 1

Supervisor name: **Dr Celia Antoniou**

Supervisor comments:

Approved

Supervisor/first reviewer signature: **Dr Celia Antoniou**

Date: **08/05/2024**

Reviewer 2

Advisory committee/course team member name: **Dr Yasemin Yildiz**

Advisory committee/course team member comments:

Approved subject to revisions

Please make the changes requested in the annotated comments. Also, insert all the attachments to the ethics form, so it is one text.

Advisory committee/course team member signature:

Date: **10/05/24**

Decision on behalf of reviewers

Approved

Referred back to applicant and supervisor

Referred to the REC for review

Recording

Recorded in the student information system

Once completed and approved, please send this form and associated documents to the relevant programme administrator to record on the student information system and to securely store.

Further guidance on ethical issues can be found on the UCL Institute of Education Research Ethics Committee website

Appendix 7: Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet for Thai postgraduates studying in the TESOL program in the United Kingdom

UCL Research Ethics Committee Approval ID Number: _____

YOU WILL BE GIVEN A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET

Title of Study:

A study examining the foreign language classroom anxiety and enjoyment in relation to speaking skills of Thai postgraduates studying in the TESOL program in the United Kingdom

Department: School of Culture, Communication and Media, Institute of Education

Name and Contact Details of the Researcher(s):

The Researcher: Seksan Thongthai (dtnvt8@ucl.ac.uk)

The Supervisor: Dr. Celia-Vasiliki Antoniou (celia.antoniou@ucl.ac.uk)

Details of the Principal Researcher: Mr. Seksan Thongthai, an in-service English teacher, at the department of foreign languages at Pibulwitthayalai School, Lopburi, Thailand.

1. Invitation Paragraph

You have been kindly invited to contribute to a valuable corpus of study by participating in a comprehensive study that aims to explore the foreign language classroom anxiety and enjoyment in relation to speaking skills. This research will take the form of questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, which will include both led questions and open-end discussions. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish before making the decision. Your understand of the extent and nature of this research's procedures is value to us. Furthermore, do not hesitate to contact me or other researchers for more information or guidance. You are welcome to share your opportunity to participate in research with others. Your participation in the study is completely voluntary and we thank you for considering the invitation. You are free to decide whether to participate in our research study and take your time to decide.

2. What is the project's purpose?

The study is designed to delve into the nuanced interplay between emotions and language learning by examining Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety (FLCA) and Foreign Language Enjoyment (FLE) in relation to speaking skills among Thai postgraduate TESOL learners in the UK. It endeavours to outline the emotional profiles of these learners and investigate the intricate relationship between anxiety and enjoyment as they pertain to the development of speaking skills. The aim is to illuminate the emotional landscape of language acquisition, identifying both impediments and catalysts to inform and refine teaching methods, curriculum design, and policy-making in ESL environments. With a timeline beginning in May and concluding in August, the study not only seeks to contribute to academic discourse but also to arm educators and policymakers with actionable insights to enhance learner engagement and outcomes in TESOL programs.

3. Why have I been chosen?

As a participant, you have been selected for this study because your background and current experiences directly correspond with the research objectives. As a Thai postgraduate TESOL learner in the UK, you represent the very demographic this study aims to understand in terms of language speaking skills and the emotional factors that influence them, such as classroom anxiety and enjoyment.

Your first-hand experiences with speaking anxiety in various academic settings like lectures, seminars, and group assignments are at the core of why this research is pertinent to you. Your perspective is invaluable, particularly because it is believed that your experiences will resonate with the phenomena being explored, such as the apprehension felt when speaking in a second language and the enjoyment that can come from successful communication.

Regarding the study's criteria, you fit the inclusion parameters that are crucial for a comprehensive analysis of the research questions. Your experiences and the challenges you face are mirrored by others in similar situations; thus, understanding your perspective could provide insights that are relevant to a wider audience.

In terms of recruitment scale, you are among an anticipated group of 14 to 20 participants. This number has been selected to ensure a range of experiences are captured while maintaining the study's manageability and depth of engagement with each participant.

4. Do I have to take part?

Your choice to join this study is entirely up to you. Remember, if you choose to participate, you are doing so willingly, and if at any time you wish to stop, you're completely free to without any drawbacks. There will not be any sort of penalty or loss of the benefits you have a right to if you decide not to take part or if you start but then decide to step back at any point. Also, it is your call to say what happens with the data you have already provided if you decide to withdraw. Your well-being and comfort are the most important aspects here.

5. What will happen to me if I take part?

If I agree to take part in this study, I will be involved from the start of the data collection period in May until the study concludes in August. During this time, I will be asked to complete a set of questionnaires just once. These are designed to measure my levels of enjoyment and anxiety in the language classroom, particularly related to speaking skills. If my responses to the questionnaires stand out, I may also be invited to participate in an audio-recorded, semi-structured interview. The interview is intended to explore my personal experiences and perspectives in greater depth.

As a participant, I will not be required to commit to any regular or long-term engagements – it is a one-time questionnaire completion and potentially a single interview session. The questionnaires should take a reasonable amount of time that will not significantly disrupt my daily schedule, and the interview will be scheduled at a mutually convenient time. All of this will take place without the need for travel, as it can be done online.

6. Will I be recorded and how will the recorded media be used?

If I participate and my interview is audio-recorded, these recordings will be used strictly for research analysis and potentially as examples during conference presentations or academic lectures. My consent is key, and outside of these stated uses, my recordings will not be used for anything else unless I give written permission. Also, access to the original recordings will be tightly controlled, ensuring that only those directly involved in the project can listen to them.

7. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

As a participant in this study, I can be reassured that there are no anticipated disadvantages or risks to my involvement. The researcher has put measures in place to ensure my experience is safe and secure, and my personal information and responses will be handled with the utmost confidentiality. I understand that every aspect of the study has been carefully considered to protect my well-being and privacy.

8. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

By participating in this study, I have the opportunity to contribute to a deeper understanding of speaking anxiety in language learning. My experiences could provide valuable data that may shape future research and interventions aimed at reducing speaking anxiety. This could lead to more effective teaching strategies and learning environments that are responsive to the emotional needs of language learners like me.

9. What if something goes wrong?

If I have any concerns or complaints about how I am being treated during this study, or if something serious happens that I believe is connected to my participation, I know exactly whom to reach out to. I would first contact the researcher, Seksan Thongthai, at dtvnst8@ucl.ac.uk, or the Supervisor, Dr Celia-Vasiliki Antoniou, at celia.antoniou@ucl.ac.uk. They are the initial points of contact for any concerns.

If I feel that my complaint has not been adequately addressed by them, I have the right to escalate the matter to the Chair of the UCL Research Ethics Committee at ethics@ucl.ac.uk. It is reassuring to know there is a clear process for addressing complaints, ensuring that any issues I might have will be taken seriously and handled properly.

10. Will my taking part in this project be kept confidential?

Any information collected about me for this research will be held with the strictest confidence. I have been assured that I won't be identifiable in any reports or publications resulting from the study. Moreover, to ensure my privacy, the data will be password-protected, and access will be restricted solely to the researcher and the supervisor. It is clear that the responsibility for maintaining confidentiality lies with the researcher, not just the Research Ethics Committee, so I can participate knowing that legal and regulatory requirements for data protection are taken seriously and followed meticulously.

11. Limits to confidentiality

- Please note that assurances on confidentiality will be strictly adhered to unless evidence of wrongdoing or potential harm is uncovered. In such cases the University may be obliged to contact relevant statutory bodies/agencies.
- Please note that confidentiality will be maintained as far as it is possible, unless during our conversation I hear anything which makes me worried that someone might be in danger of harm, I might have to inform relevant agencies of this.
- Please note that confidentiality may not be guaranteed, due to the limited size of the participant sample.

12. Use of Deception

I have been informed that the specific objectives of this study may not be fully disclosed to me until after my participation has concluded. I understand the general tasks I am to perform; however, the comprehensive intentions behind the study will only be revealed to me at the end of the research process. Once I have been fully briefed on the intent of the study, I will have the opportunity to withdraw my data if I wish to do so.

13. What will happen to the results of the research project?

The results from this research project are expected to be compiled and published after the study's conclusion. Participants like me will be able to access a copy of the results upon publication. I will be informed of the role I played in the study but will remain anonymous in any report or publication that comes from this research.

Furthermore, I understand that the data collected may be stored and could potentially be used for future research, in line with UCL guidelines. The data will be kept securely and anonymously for a period of one year to ensure compliance with these policies.

14. Local Data Protection Privacy Notice

Notice:

The controller for this project will be University College London (UCL). The UCL Data Protection Officer provides oversight of UCL activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at data-protection@ucl.ac.uk

This 'local' privacy notice sets out the information that applies to this particular study. Further information on how UCL uses participant information can be found in our 'general' privacy notice:

For participants in research studies, click [here](#)

The information that is required to be provided to participants under data protection legislation (GDPR and DPA 2018) is provided across both the ‘local’ and ‘general’ privacy notices.

The categories of personal data used will be as follows:

Name
Address

...

The lawful basis that would be used to process your *personal data* will be performance of a task in the public interest.

The lawful basis used to process *special category personal data* will be for scientific and historical research or statistical purposes.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, or if you would like to contact us about your rights, please contact UCL in the first instance at data-protection@ucl.ac.uk.

Detail any intended recipients of personal data if not explained elsewhere, and also advise if any personal data will be transferred outside the EEA, and if so to where.

Who is organising and funding the research?

-

15. Contact for further information

If I have any further questions or need more information about this research, I can contact the researcher, Seksan Thongthai, at dtvst8@ucl.ac.uk, or the supervisor, Dr. Celia-Vasiliki Antoniou, at celia.antoniou@ucl.ac.uk. Before participating, I will be asked to read and sign a consent form, which I will also receive a copy of, along with the information sheet about the study.

I would like to express my gratitude for considering me for participation in this study. Your participation is highly valued and contributes significantly to the research. Thank you for your time and contribution to this important work.

Thank you for reading this information sheet and for considering to take part in this research study.

Appendix 8: Consent Form

CONSENT FORM FOR THAI POSTGRADUATES STUDYING IN THE TESOL PROGRAM IN THE UNITED KINGDOM RESEARCH STUDIES

Please complete this form after you have read the Information Sheet and/or listened to an explanation about the research.

Title of Study: A study examining the foreign language classroom anxiety and enjoyment in relation to speaking skills of Thai postgraduates studying in the TESOL program in the United Kingdom

Department: School of Culture, Communication and Media, Institute of Education

Name and Contact Details of the Researcher(s): Seksan Thongthai (dtnvst8@ucl.ac.uk)

Name and Contact Details of the Principal Researcher: Seksan Thongthai (dtnvst8@ucl.ac.uk) the Supervisor: Dr. Celia-Vasiliki Antoniou (celia.antoniou@ucl.ac.uk)

Name and Contact Details of the UCL Data Protection Officer:

This study has been approved by the UCL Research Ethics Committee: Project ID number: _____

Thank you for considering taking part in this research. The person organising the research must explain the project to you before you agree to take part. If you have any questions arising from the Information Sheet or explanation already given to you, please ask the researcher before you decide whether to join in. You will be given a copy of this Consent Form to keep and refer to at any time.

I confirm that I understand that by ticking/initialling each box below I am consenting to this element of the study. I understand that it will be assumed that unticked/initialled boxes means that I DO NOT consent to that part of the study. I understand that by not giving consent for any one element that I may be deemed ineligible for the study.

		Tick Box
1.	<p>*I confirm that I have read and understood the Information Sheet for the above study. I have had an opportunity to consider the information and what will be expected of me. I have also had the opportunity to ask questions which have been answered to my satisfaction</p> <p><i>[and would like to take part in (please tick one or more of the following)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a set of questionnaires - a semi-structured interview 	
2.	*I understand that I will be able to withdraw my data up to one year after interview	
3.	*I consent to participate in the study. I understand that my personal information (<i>provide information on what personal information specifically will be collected</i>) will be used for the purposes explained to me. I understand that according to data protection legislation, 'public task' will be the lawful basis for processing.	
4.	Use of the information for this project only	

	<p>*I understand that all personal information will remain confidential and that all efforts will be made to ensure I cannot be identified (<i>unless you state otherwise, because of the research design or except as required by law</i>).</p> <p>I understand that my data gathered in this study will be stored anonymously and securely. It will not be possible to identify me in any publications.</p>	
5.	*I understand that my information may be subject to review by responsible individuals from the University for monitoring and audit purposes.	
6.	<p>*I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason, without the care I receive or my legal rights being affected.</p> <p>I understand that if I decide to withdraw, any personal data I have provided up to that point will be deleted unless I agree otherwise.</p>	
7.	I understand the potential risks of participating and the support that will be available to me should I become distressed during the course of the research.	
8.	I understand that the data will not be made available to any commercial organisations but is solely the responsibility of the researcher(s) undertaking this study.	
9.	I understand that I will not benefit financially from this study or from any possible outcome it may result in in the future.	
10.	I agree that my anonymised research data may be used by others for future research. [No one will be able to identify you when this data is shared.]	
11.	I understand that the information I have submitted will be published as a report and I wish to receive a copy of it. Yes/No	
12.	<p>I consent to my interview being audio/video recorded and understand that the recordings will be:</p> <p>EITHER</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stored anonymously, using password-protected software and will be used for training, quality control, audit and specific research purposes. <p>To note: If you do not want your participation recorded you can still take part in the study.</p>	
13.	I hereby confirm that I understand the inclusion criteria as detailed in the Information Sheet and explained to me by the researcher.	
14.	<p>I hereby confirm that:</p> <p>(a) I understand the exclusion criteria as detailed in the Information Sheet and explained to me by the researcher; and</p> <p>(b) I do not fall under the exclusion criteria.</p>	
15.	I am aware of who I should contact if I wish to lodge a complaint.	
16.	I voluntarily agree to take part in this study.	
17.	<p>Use of information for this project and beyond</p> <p>I would be happy for the data I provide to be archived at School of Culture, Communication and Media, Institute of Education, UCL. Audio and related data will be stored anonymously, using password-protected software for up to 12 months.</p> <p>I understand that other authenticated researchers will have access to my anonymised data.</p>	

If you would like your contact details to be retained so that you can be contacted in the future by UCL researchers who would like to invite you to participate in follow up studies to this project, or in future studies of a similar nature, please tick the appropriate box below.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes, I would be happy to be contacted in this way	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	No, I would not like to be contacted	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Appendix 9: Research Proposal

DISSERTATION PROPOSAL

Provisional title

A study examining the foreign language classroom anxiety and enjoyment in relation to speaking skills of Thai postgraduates studying in the TESOL program in the United Kingdom

Research area

Learner / Teacher emotions

Interest

Positive psychology has put much focus on the roles played by positive and negative emotions in foreign language learning. Dörnyei and Ryan (2015) further point out that this area has mainly been neglected by scholars of second language acquisition due to traditional reasons related to emphasizing cognitive aspects. As posited by MacIntyre and Gregersen (2012), positive emotions would result in enlarged perspectives by learners; whereas those with negative predispose learners to a narrowed perspective and restricted input of language.

My study will only further investigate the interaction between anxiety and enjoyment, classroom-related states, and its effects on the speaking skills of Thai students in TESOL studying in the UK. It was aimed at establishing which specific issues and factors can contribute both to enjoyment and to effective learning; in doing so, it provides important insights for the further development of more effective international curricula by universities and policymakers.

Thus, emotional experiences become one of the important factors in the process of foreign language learning as they directly affect a learner's motivation and outcomes. Understanding these emotional dynamics can also give teachers insight into improved instructional strategies, thus minimizing the negative impacts of anxiety and boredom and maximizing motivational energy. After almost six years of teaching the English language in Thailand, it became clear to me that emotions are a critical aspect of learning a language. This time, the reverse situation that causes poor learning, at other times results in poor performance, especially in passive learning set-ups such as some EFL lectures. These help bring out the argument better for me: learners can get a good understanding and grasp of what they learn when motivated, not any less than when motivated by negative feelings as cited, feelings like anxiety and boredom.

It is high time that more focused research went into these dynamics. It is research of this nature that can create awareness for the role that emotional elements play in learning achievements. This realization is able to give insight in the better formulation of teaching methods and, eventually, learner success when it comes to foreign language acquisition. Fear of speaking in class due to anxiety inhibits many students from doing so for fear of being judged or making a mistake, thus stifling language development and confidence.

My research aims at applying quantitative measures to quantify the levels of anxiety and enjoyment among students, focusing on the use of tools such as the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale for quantifying anxiety along with newly developed instruments for assessing enjoyment. This data will be correlated with speaking test scores to examine the direct and indirect effects of these emotions on language proficiency.

Besides recording quantitative measures, qualitative interviews will also be conducted to get deeper into the personal experiences and the perceptions of students about their emotional states in language acquisition. The situational causes of anxiety and enjoyment triggered by specific methods of teaching or classroom activities would be revealed in the interviews.

This research is expected to give empirical evidence in support of the importance of educational practice focusing on developing a positive emotional environment within language learning. This could be put into practice by training teachers to know how to spot potential signs of emotional distress and how to modify their teaching practices to create an increasingly engaging and supporting classroom environment. This, therefore, will give credence to integrating emotional intelligence training into teacher education programs aimed at turning out in-service teachers who would have skills to effectively manage their emotions and those of the learners.

This overall approach will further not just advance the area of understanding the affective landscape within foreign language classrooms but may also benefit the empowerment of language education policies and practices that are more effective, thereby supporting students academically and with their emotional welfare.

Provisional research questions (main and subsidiary).

1. What are the general profiles of FLE and FLCA specifically in relation to speaking skills among Thai postgraduate TESOL learners based in the UK?
2. What are the relationships between FLE and FLCA with a specific focus on speaking skills among these individuals?
3. According to the learners, what are the sources of FLE and FLCA when it comes to speaking skills?

Brief literature review

Research on language anxiety, in particular during the process of learning and using a second or foreign language, has been developed by a number of studies and research works that have tried to identify and find solutions to this widespread educational and psychological issue. A ground-breaking work by Horwitz et al. (1986) in designing the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) marked a turning point in identifying and quantifying specific anxiety triggers related to language learning. High anxiety scores were specifically those related to speaking off the cuff or feeling at a loss when talking in class.

Horwitz et al. (2010) further explored the concept of speaking anxiety, identifying that it had negative effects not only on academic achievement but also on the general psychological health of language learners.

They pointed out that the public nature of speaking tasks in educational contexts magnifies the anxiety of learners, since such tasks usually require the student to come face-to-face with his linguistic inadequacies. Horwitz (1995) also cited communicative settings as specific breeding grounds for anxiety, where being expected to perform in public in the target language could elicit a great emotional reaction and consequently pose a threat to language learning. Dewaele and Saito (2024) went on to deconstruct the specificity of "foreign language classroom anxiety" (FLCA) and highlighted the comprehensive nature of such anxiety, including a learner's self-perception, beliefs, feelings, and behaviors that uniquely arise from the learning process.

Dewaele and MacIntyre (2014) gave a more in-depth view of FLCA in their statement that FLCA also operates concurrently with another construct, Foreign Language Enjoyment (FLE), that is may be potential determinants of the willingness to communicate a learner might possess. A crucial willingness to communicate, WTC is influenced by affective-cognitive contexts, motivational

tendencies, and situational antecedents. Several studies have shown the complex relation between classroom environment, learner emotions, and WTC. Studies conducted by Dewaele and Dewaele (2018), MacIntyre and Doucette (2010), and Cao (2011) found that FLCA can serve as a major deterrent to WTC.

Contrastingly, positive predictors that were noted to boost it was the frequency of the use of the foreign language by the teacher and a socially pleasant classroom climate. These are further confirmed by the meta-analysis of Shirvan et al., in which perceived communicative competence, motivation, and FLCA were found to be strong determinants of WTC. Language learning anxiety was elaborated to be influenced by trait emotional intelligence (TEI) through Li in 2018 and Chen et al. in 2024. TEI was shown to be inversely related with levels of foreign language and speaking anxiety—the higher the TEI, the lower the levels of anxiety—in these two research experiments. TEI did, to a general end, buffer anxiety, not only acting as a mediator for the impact of anxiety on language achievement. This evidence underscores the value of TEI in educational settings, where higher emotional intelligence can alleviate some of the common hurdles encountered in language learning.

The relationship between personality traits and language classroom emotions has also been studied extensively. Researchers like Dewaele (2023) have investigated how traits such as extraversion and openness to experience correlate with speaking anxiety. These studies have found that certain personality profiles can significantly affect how learners experience and manage anxiety, thus impacting their overall language learning process and outcomes.

Continuing this exploration, Dewaele et al. (2018) looked at how both teacher and learner variables contribute to Foreign Language Enjoyment (FLE) and Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety (FLCA). Their findings suggest that an effective teacher who sparks student interest and fosters a positive classroom environment can greatly reduce anxiety and enhance enjoyment and engagement in language learning.

Expanding the scope to different cultural and linguistic contexts, Chen, Chen, and Liu (2023) examined Chinese university students learning German. Their study highlighted that while teacher-related factors were pivotal in boosting FLE, learner-related factors were more influential in affecting FLCA. They stressed the importance of teachers in creating a learning environment that promotes enjoyment and reduces anxiety by facilitating interaction and incorporating cultural content into the curriculum.

Tsang and Dewaele (2023) further added to this dialogue by exploring the interplay between classroom emotions such as anxiety, boredom, and enjoyment,

and their impact on language proficiency among young learners. They identified enjoyment as a critical predictor of both engagement and proficiency, suggesting that positive emotions can override negative ones such as anxiety and boredom.

In a novel approach, Dewaele and Dewaele (2017) used an idiodynamic method to monitor real-time shifts in enjoyment and anxiety during language tasks. This method revealed complex patterns of emotional fluctuation, challenging the traditional view that enjoyment and anxiety in language learning are inversely related.

On a longitudinal scale, Pan and Zhang (2021) tracked the stability of FLE and FLA over time among Chinese university students learning English, tying these emotional states to motivational factors and personality traits such as extraversion. These insights are invaluable for language educators aiming to tailor their teaching strategies to better support and enhance the learning experience.

In conclusion, the ongoing research in the field of language anxiety and enjoyment not only sheds light on the profound influence these emotions have on learning outcomes but also serves as a critical foundation for developing educational strategies that support both the linguistic and emotional well-being of learners. By understanding and addressing these complex relationships, educators can foster a more inclusive and effective language learning environment.

Proposed methodology

An integrated mixed-method approach will be employed to gather and analyse both qualitative and quantitative data.

Two questionnaires are utilized in the qualitative phase:

1. Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS): This scale includes six speaking-related items adapted from the original Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale by Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986). Respondents are asked to assess each item using a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 represents 'strongly disagree' and 5 'strongly agree'.

2. Foreign Language Enjoyment (FLE) Scale: Originally developed by Dewaele and MacIntyre in 2014, this scale is also based on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), enabling participants to express their level of enjoyment during the language learning process.

Subsequently, semi-structured interviews will be conducted. These are particularly effective for exploring underlying motivations, coping mechanisms, and contextual factors that influence emotional experiences in language learning, as highlighted by Dörnyei (2005).

Data collection and analysis

The volunteers will be chosen via snowball sampling. The calls for research will be distributed through emails, social media, and personal contacts. The subjects will fill out an online survey questionnaire. Those who have excellent response in some demographics as per the scoring will be selected for an online personal interview. It is estimated that 14-20 Thai TESOL students will take part who are living in the UK.

The responses to questionnaires from all the participants will be statistically analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). For the interviews, audio recording will help to capture contents in their actual form, and content analysis techniques will be applied.

This detailed statistical analysis will involve both descriptive statistics, which are inferential, in order to ensure that the data collected is well understood. Descriptive statistics will provide summaries about the sample and the measures.

This will also allow drawing inferences on the basis of the effect of particular variables on language learning anxiety and enjoyment. This dual approach will aid in clearly specifying the relationships between variables, and hence yield a thorough analysis of the interrelationship between anxiety, enjoyment, and language performance of the participants. The data yielded in the interview will be literally documented and will then be analysed systematically to recognize recurring themes or patterns related to experiences and perceptions. Such qualitative analysis complements the quantitative data by gaining deeper insights into personal and emotional aspects of language learning, which could hardly be elicited by survey responses alone.

The data drawn from both the quantitative and qualitative sources will be integrated to ensure an increase in understanding of the factors associated with success in learning languages by Thai TESOL students in the United Kingdom. This approach in methodology can grant the study an overview that could be amenable to educational practices and policy affairs, aiming toward improved language learning settings and reduced learning impediments. Therefore, the research is bound to furnish information useful for the fields of language education and educational psychology that will help contribute to further develop

more effective and empathetic teaching strategies tailored to better suit the needs of international students enrolled in TESOL programs.

Ethics

It is necessary for the study, just like any other piece of scientific research, to take into account the significance and absolute need of the ethical issues that are encountered and to treat them in an acceptable manner. Under these circumstances, the participants will be made aware of the objectives and goals of the research, their consent will be obtained once they have been fully informed, and their anonymity will be protected. The participants will be selected using a method known as purposive sampling, and they will be made aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any point in time, should they so desire.

Time-line

- Early April: Work on research proposal, ethics form, consent form, and information sheet.
- Mid April: Revise research proposal, ethics form, consent form, and information sheet
- Early May: Revise ethics form, consent form, and information sheet in response to feedback, finalise data collection instruments, begin writing literature review.
- Mid May: Collect data, data analysis, write methodology chapter, literature review progress report, data collection progress report.
- Early-June: General progress report, finish literature review, methodology progress report and finish data analyses.
- Mid June: Write the findings and discussion chapters
- Early-July: Have my conclusions ready and should be ready to discuss the implications of your research and its limitations.
- Mid-July: submit first dissertation draft
- August: Revise dissertation based on feedback.
- Mid August: Hand in the final version of dissertation.

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